

Kate Sato

Registration no.109025710

**What are the Enablers and Constraints Affecting Institutional
Improvement at Hokubetsu University? A Case Study of Native
English Instructors in a Japanese University.**

**Dissertation submitted in partial fulfilment
of the degree of the MSc in Educational Leadership**

January 2015

Word count: 19,942

Table of Contents

Acknowledgements	4
Abstract	5
Introduction	6
Literature Review	12
Japanese Leadership in Business	13
Japanese Leadership in Education	16
Organizational Culture	17
Organizational Culture and Change	23
Leadership, Collaboration , Teamwork & Change	25
Teamwork	26
Multiculturalism & Teamwork	28
National Cultures & Cultural Intelligence	29
Methodology	33
Paradigm	34
Approach: Case Study	35
Methods: Qualitative	35
Ethics	39
Data Collection	42
Authenticity	43
Validity	44
Positionality	45
Triangulation	46
Data Analysis	46
Analysis	48
Presentation of Findings	50
What Factors are Contributing to Institutional Improvement?	50
Organisational Culture	50
Leadership	51
Teamwork	51
What Factors are Impeding Institutional Improvement?	52

Acknowledgements

I am indebted to a number of people for their support. I would like to thank Professor. Barker for his encouragement, support, and guidance, without which this investigation would have not materialised. Also, I would like to thank Shuhei, and my children for their sacrifices and understanding. I am grateful to Matt, Don & Pete for their tolerance and forbearance throughout, to Tim for his consistent advice, to J.C. for giving me inspiration, the participants who generously gave their time, and others who live around me whose faith and understanding carried me through.

.

Abstract

When people from different parts of the world find themselves working together there are a number of potential obstacles to smooth and efficient collaboration such as cultural differences between the members in the group, the leadership and management of the group, as well as social order within the group. When such a group functions in a multicultural setting the potential for complexity increases. This qualitative investigation based on individual, semi-structured interviews adopted a case study approach which examined possible factors impeding and facilitating improvement amongst a group of native English instructors working together in one Japanese university. With the early retirement of a native English speaking professor, and apparent disharmony within the group of native English instructors, this research highlights the incompatibility between the organizational culture in this Japanese university and the group of western instructors that are employed within. Successful integration of this group of western instructors requires attention, yet remains neglected. Japanese institutions concerned with the employing numbers of western instructors are recommended to give attention to managing their leadership.

organizational culture, Japanese higher education, culture, leadership, teamwork

Introduction

When people from different parts of the world find themselves working together there are a number of potential obstacles to smooth and efficient collaboration (Schein, 2010a) such as cultural differences between the members in the group (Cox, 1991), the leadership and management of the group, as well as social order within the group (Schein, 2010a). When a group functions in a multicultural setting the potential for complexity increases. This study focuses on a group of native English instructors (NEI) all employed in one Japanese university at the same time. Coming from four countries, with various backgrounds, and having spent varying lengths of time in the Japanese culture, the NEI had different degrees of Japanese language skills. With apparent frustrations observed, and general lack of harmony within the group, this study investigates what the NEI say about their experience of working in the university with the aim of uncovering and illuminating underlying factors facilitating and hindering institutional improvement amongst the group of NEI, and analysing how those factors affect organizational culture, leadership and teamwork, so that suggestions for promoting institutional improvement can be proposed.

English language education in Japanese higher education has been under scrutiny in recent years as government measures to increase students' abilities to communicate in English have gained momentum (Hashimoto, 2009). Simultaneously, other external pressures, such as the reduction in the population of students entering university, are adding increased pressure to higher educational institutions as they find themselves vying to fulfil student quotas (Kariya, 2012). While complacency kills change, this unstable situation has the potential to open the door for change and improvement (Kotter, 2012) not only among groups like the NEI, but

also institutions. However, in organizational change organizational culture is of paramount importance as it has the potential to impede change (ibid). Another key factor is leadership as leaders transmit 'beliefs, values and assumptions' (Schein, 2010a: 235) that may become integrated and shared by the group. Within HU (Hokubetsu University, a pseudonym), the NEI face increasing pressure due to the perception that English should not be required for all courses. Ultimately these factors determine tighter budgets, a reduction in the number of English classes, and thus fewer jobs. Therefore, the internal structures and ways of functioning, which determine how the institution responds to both external and internal pressures, affects the NEI.

The retirement of a long-standing native English professor in the university coupled with apparent frustrations expressed by some teachers within the group prompted this enquiry. Fourteen, out of fifteen, NEI who were working in a university of about 125 full-time faculty and approximately 3,500 students, participated in this investigation and included a mix of full-time (five) and part-time (nine) instructors. The predominantly male NEI, were from the USA, Canada, UK and New Zealand. They differed in levels of: qualifications, teaching experience in the host culture, and years of teaching in the university. The university was founded about seventy years prior to the study and is a middle ranking university offering undergraduate studies in eight fields with a narrower range of post graduate options. The university is run in a cooperative manner, like many Japanese educational institutions (Tuneyoshi, 2001) where decision making comes out of the harmony and unity of the group within departments, and where heads of departments are voted in for the posts by their colleagues. These posts are held for two years, including the post of President of the university.

Positionality influences a number of areas in a case study: how the study is approached, the 'research participant involved', how the data is interpreted, and the outcome of the case study (Mills et al., 2009: 886). Being a Caucasian woman, raised in the UK, having lived approximately half of my life out of the UK, and with about twenty years work experience in Japan, plus having fluent Japanese language skills, this experience brings an appreciation for the Japanese culture whilst still being able to understand the western mindset. It is this appreciation and understanding that underpins this research. At the start of this investigation while working part-time in the institution it was relatively easy to remain detached from the data. However, being ushered into a full-time position, the demands of the case study increased as 'delicate judgement calls' (Yin, 2013: 72) were required. Living in the milieu on a daily basis and then after work remaining in the milieu through the data, was at times extremely challenging. Struggling with working through the desire to protect those that had entrusted me with the data they had divulged, and yet knowing that a consistent, and accurate portrayal of the data was needed, along with being an inexperienced researcher, caused great demands. I found myself wrestling with why some issues had not been openly discussed and resolved, but rather left festering and unattended to. Yet, it was from this place of contention I came to see that much of the data was the result of a lack of frameworks and systems in the organizational culture that left grey areas which had ultimately become breeding grounds for issues to fester in.

With this research taking place in a Japanese university, the concept of Japanese leadership is of fundamental importance as it differs greatly to leadership in the West. Japanese leadership has eluded western researchers as they have sought to understand it through western concepts (Hofstede, 1993). In recent years more Japanese researchers have

published on Japanese leadership opening a way for a deeper understanding (Hasegawa, 2010). Leadership in Japanese higher education, however, is relatively unexplored by western researchers. However, the styles of leadership adopted, and how they are distributed in the university will affect groups of people, or teams, and their development (Harris, 2010).

A number of Japanese researchers have highlighted issues in traditional Japanese universities (Ogawa, 2002) and have commented on the government reforms affecting universities (Itoh, 2002). The upper echelons of Japanese higher education are at a turning point (Yonezawa, 2007) but the consequence of those changes and where that leaves the middle and lower echelons does not appear to be the focus of research either past or present. Yet leaders can also influence change and provide impetus for improvement (Hallinger and Heck, 2011). To broaden the scope in this investigation, change and evidence of change were examined, as well as how it is managed, as they are relevant to this study.

Terms such as 'distributed leadership' (Harris & Mujis, 2004) and 'teacher leadership' (Harris, 2010) have emanated from the hegemony of Anglo-American perspectives (Walker, 2003) as keys to institutional improvement. Improvement and change can also lie deep within the organizational culture of an institution. Change can be found not only in the complexity of leadership, and cultural organisation, but also in the more grass-roots issues of teacher motivation and collaboration. The impact of leadership on teacher motivation, and organizational climate is substantial (Barker, 2005). Within these interlinked elements are various threats to improvement. An academic calendar, for the most part, is predictable, because year by year there is routine and little change thus creating

stability, whereas change can induce fear and stress which can arouse emotions (Smith, 2008). Nevertheless, change will be found as an institution develops (Chapman & Harris, 2004). Therefore, evidence of approaches to improvement may be found in the data.

It is expected that the range of the participants' perspectives on 'reality' that this investigation aims to describe, will be influenced by the wide variety of experiences, including their backgrounds, and cultures of origin. Taking a qualitative approach, using a case study 'strategy' (Punch, 2009: 119), data was collected from the fourteen native English teachers all working at the same institution at the same time. The data was collected using semi-structured interviews. This yielded copious quantities of qualitative data which was analysed using the Miles & Huberman (Punch, 2009) framework from which conclusions were drawn.

The investigation seeks to illuminate the participants' perceptions and understandings of the leadership and organizational culture at HU. In so doing, the hindrances and facilitators to institutional improvement were drawn from the data and analysed. In this investigation commonalities and differences between the participants' perceptions were identified in order to present an understanding of the situation from which suggestions for improvements can be made, with the aim to reducing existing barriers to institutional improvement.

The main research question for this study is:

What are the perceived enabling and constraining factors influencing institutional improvement amongst the NEI at Hokubetsu University?

Also, a more specific research question is:

How do these perceived factors impact organizational culture, leadership and teamwork?

Literature Review

This section of the investigation reviews the literature from the five areas relevant to the research questions. This provides background to this study for the collection and analysis of the data presented later. The five areas are: Japanese leadership in general and more specifically in higher institutions, organizational culture, change, teamwork & multicultural groups, and national cultures. In examining the past research in these areas, themes that may surface in the data will be illuminated. In examining issues and themes that arise in the data, against the literature outlined below, recommendations will be offered as a way forward to positively enhance institutional improvement among the NEI.

Foreigners working in Japanese universities have different experiences from when working in their own countries. One such difference is work ethic. As Tsuneyoshi (2001: 152) points out 'Japanese organisations such as the school and workplace are cooperatively organised'. However, there are more subtle differences as well: organizational culture being one. Kotter points out that culture affects 'everyone' (2012: 156) and it can be 'specific to sub-units' (ibid.); 'it can powerfully influence human behaviour' (ibid.) and 'it is difficult to change' (ibid.). Japanese leadership, and more specifically in higher educational institutions, is another difference. Related to this is change, as it is influenced by a number of factors. Furthermore, the NEI are, to some extent, despite all coming from English speaking countries, a multicultural group, and therefore may need different management styles (Appelbaum et al., 1998).

This literature review will, therefore, examine each of these in the possible role they can play in this investigation.

Japanese Leadership in Business

Nakano (1997) found that company policy was the prominent factor influencing decisions made by Japanese managers. This correlates to Hofstede & Bond's (1984) findings: Japan has a high uncertainty avoidance (UA) score which facilitates running a company from systems and ways of functioning. Thus, it is not an individual leader that determines the company policy, but a mentality of, *this is how our organisation functions*. This gives security and stability. The downside to this is that change is complicated and difficult to manoeuvre; where the authority lies and how change is implemented is dispersed through chains of groups of people. Japan also has a high 'masculinity' (MA) score (ibid.) which means the focus is set on the success (however the organisation defines success) of the company, and all members of the organisation will unquestionably devote themselves to working for its success. This explains and correlates with Hasegawa's studies of Japanese business leadership. He concluded that the hallmark that defines Japanese leadership is, 'consistent and steady management' (2010: 15). It can therefore be expected that, rather than being quickly responsive to pressures or influences, change at HU will be slow and steady.

Ouchi's (1981) analysis of differences between US and Japanese firms found seven distinct differences. In Japanese firms: employees worked longer hours, decision making was more collective, there was more collective responsibility, the process of employee evaluation and promotion was slower, the

...mechanisms of control were more explicit, the career paths were less specialised and, there was more holistic concern for employees. (Lussier & Achua, 2009: 153-4)

Delving deeper into the Japanese work ethic reveals more fundamental traits that pervade Japanese leadership.

Below the surface, Hasegawa's (2010) research hints at a very crucial point about Japanese leadership. The unspoken message that comes through the accounts of Japanese returning from overseas training, or studies, is: Japanese are willing to humble themselves, take on a different role for the company, so that in the long-term the company benefits from the personal sacrifice taken. The personal sacrifice reoccurs in the literature on Japanese universities below. This willingness and ability to humble oneself and learn from others is a critical strength for the Japanese. As Covey (1999: vii-viii) states:

When we are humble, teachable, and open ... we can experience the paradigm shifts that open up the world to us.

For decades this is what the Japanese have done and continue to do.

Taka & Foglia (1994) studied the Japanese manufacturing industries: the backbone of Japan's post-war economy (Denison and Chung, 1976). In investigating why Japanese corporations are not plagued with 'negative ethical implications' (Taka & Foglia, 1994: 135) like American corporations, they concluded it is due to leadership styles. They found Japanese leadership has three fundamental components: self-realisation, appreciation of

diverse abilities, and trust in others. They also explain the Japanese 'normative environment' (ibid., 1994: 136) as a force that is beyond oneself which influences the environment. This corresponds with Hemphill & Coons' definition of leadership that suggests that leadership can be 'the behaviour of an individual when he is directing the activities of a group toward a shared goal' (1957: 7) and not just a system.

Reinforcing this is the famous Japanese adage, *the nail that sticks out gets hammered down* which reflects a culture, and behaviour, that prioritises the group over the individual (Black et al., 1999). What this means on a practical level can be harder to grasp. Rumsey (2012: 233) notes Dorfman & House's comment that in Japanese organisations 'supervisors are expected to have precise answers to subordinates' (2004: 52). In a culture that values systems over individuality, the system will define the way of doing something which gives rise for precise answers, whereas in the West there will be a number of ways suggested, leading to less precise answers and potentially greater risk. However, risk is unwelcome to the Japanese (Hofstede & Bond, 1994). In a culture of uniformity this points to the mechanism of company policy. Nakano's (1997) findings, in which everyone dutifully puts their personal opinions and interests aside to line up with the company policy, correlates with this priority of group first.

Some western researchers have sought to find a system, or model, of Japanese leadership that can be applied elsewhere, while some have tried comparing it to western styles of leadership through their western lenses. However, the research highlighted here shows it is the way in which Japanese work together with those who are appointed leaders at that time, which can be described as more of a work ethic, or mindset, that is ingrained into the people

through Japanese culture, the education system and society in general. This is the crux of Japanese leadership. Understanding this unspoken social norm, helps in understanding other aspects of how Japanese work together, including within academia.

Japanese Leadership in Education

Turning from the foundation of leadership in Japanese businesses, leadership in Japanese Higher Education (HE) is now examined. Seeing how Japanese universities function will help understand the backdrop of this research paper and add depth to the findings.

Ogawa (2002) states private Japanese universities are changing their organizational structures for the first time in 100 years. This signifies two important points. First, while Japanese businesses may have changed, or adapted, in more recent years, this is not the case in Japanese HE. Therefore, although it is useful to examine Japanese business models, the extent to which they are applicable in the higher education sector is therefore limited. Second, Japanese HE appears to have made modifications, but lacks significant change (McVeigh, 2002). Therefore, it is no surprise to find a lack of literature about change in Japanese private universities.

The Japanese work ethic remains the same regardless of sector. The sacrifice of self interests for the better of the whole exists in Japanese higher educational institutions. Nagatomo recounts the story of a president of a Japanese university complaining about a lecturer who 'backed out of a lecture she was supposed to take part in' (2012: 144) because it was on a weekend that conflicted with a once-in-a-lifetime family event. The president is quoted,

saying of her, that she was acting 'irresponsibly' (ibid.). While this may be hard for the western mind to grasp, it is evidence of the mindset pervading academia.

Ogawa (2002) highlights a difference between leadership in US and Japanese universities. He states a university president in the US has administration, financial and academic roles. In a Japanese university it appears the presidents do not have the equivalent financial prowess, nor do they have influence over 'academic issues' (ibid.: 102). For private universities, however, the president, or a committee, or another top officer who is strong-willed, might wield the power to make decisions regarding policies or other key factors (McVeigh, 2002). So, with possibly no financial authority, some presidents of Japanese universities have limited influence on academics.

The literature shows the work ethic in Japanese business exists in academia too: total commitment to the cause with unwavering dedication is expected of staff. Indication of failure to give commitment is viewed disparagingly. Nevertheless, the extent to which some NEI are acculturated will doubtlessly affect other native English instructors.

Organizational Culture

Fey & Denison (2003) found evidence for applying American theories of organizational culture to Russian contexts. Like Russians, Japanese are a group-minded people (Black et al., 1999). Therefore, building on the premise that organizational cultural theory from the West can be applied elsewhere, this review looks at some studies.

Three main cultures in an organisation tend to be 'entrenched in their particular assumptions' (Schein, 2010b: 37). The first, Schein calls the 'operator culture' (ibid.):

'Every organisation develops an internal culture based on its operational success' (ibid.). Critical elements for the smooth running of the operator culture, which is based on people interacting with one another, are: 'communication, trust and teamwork' (ibid.: 44). He likens this culture to the teaching staff in a university. The second is the engineering culture (or those that drive the core technologies) and the last is the executive culture or the management. These latter two cultures focus more on the financial aspect of an organisation. Big organisations become depersonalized, and routines and rituals become prominent. Hierarchy outweighs community, and jobs and their functions become priority over individuals. This surfaces in Nagatomo's (2012) studies mentioned above. Schein (2010b) illustrates that health care is a victim of this system, and points out that the same occurs in the education sector between teachers, students and school administrators.

To overcome this disjointed functionality, learning has to take place. Each culture has something to offer, and through learning and self-examination they can work more closely together. In order for organizational learning to take place, the first necessity that Schein (2010b) points out is, the three cultures must be aligned with each other. Some hindrances arise with cultures and subcultures in organisations, such as communication barriers, decision making and the implementation of decisions. Goals may differ, and wording from department to department may also differ, leading to misunderstandings. Those that share similar experiences may create a subculture, which points to Smith's (1992) work mentioned in this review. Hence we can see that there are many obstacles that can hinder the smooth running and operations of an organisation. Evidence of any of these in the data will point to areas that can be improved.

Differences in working practices that have arisen from looking at Japanese and western cultures are relevant to this study. Three substantially different elements include leadership, which has been discussed, and decision making, priorities (Lincoln & Kalleberg, 1990) and change which we now examine.

Decision making in the Japanese culture is different from that in the West. Smith points out that,

it requires that one can understand and cope with the processes of communication and decision-making in settings where these are achieved in a different manner (1992: 48).

In relating the Japanese concept of group decision making (called the ringi system) Lincoln & Kalleberg (1990) said they 'found a strong correlation between' the ringi system and decentralization. Japanese decision making is distributed, being made by the group as a whole, rather than the final decision being left with the leader. Where decision making is achieved in a different manner, Smith (1992) found it necessary for one to also understand, as well as contend with, difficulties in communication processes. Being able to do this aids 'working effectively across different cultures' (ibid.: 48)

Priorities in western and collectivist cultures differ (Smith, 1992). Relationship has priority over task in the East; it is the opposite in the West. This is realised in the difference in conflict resolution. In Japan, rather than directly disagreeing with a colleague, other methods are used: e.g. silence (ibid.). Peaceful agreement is priority for the Japanese. Japanese prioritise building long-term relationships, whereas British and American

counterparts prioritise quick agreements. The result is a difference in negotiating styles. Westerners may have their patience tested as they work through 'lengthy' negotiations experienced when working in Japanese environments. The long-term perspective is also evident in rewards. In many Japanese companies, workers start on lower wages, and the company gives rewards and bonuses based on the number of years the employee has worked at the company. Although it can be argued this might be changing, it is still evident in Japan (Haghirian, 2010).

Improving something suggests change but not all change leads to improvement. Thus, change will be examined so as to shed light on the situation at HU. There are a number of aspects to change. Perhaps one of the most fundamental building blocks is that change needs to be managed (Kotter, 1996). This implies it is not a natural, evolutionary process in organisations, but that it needs to be implemented and overseen. From this stems the management of change which leads to differentiating between management and leadership. While managers appear to work in a context, rather than on it (Knight & Trowler, 2000) in HE, leadership is generally focused on a department, or a subunit of a department. Middlehurst & Elton (1992) recommend that management roles and leadership roles should be separated in order to maintain balance on their respective objectives. It is possible that when the balance between leadership and management are not maintained negative repercussions arise such as a loss in morale (ibid.). Smith (2008) also makes the distinction between leadership and management: it is the leaders that lead the change, while the managers who manage the change. Even if the distinction between leaders and managers is made, there seems to lie a much greater hurdle:

... changing the performances and cultures of university managers without also changing their gender and ethnic composition, selection procedures and training, may prove as intractable as changing the performances and cultures of university staff is proving to be for many existing higher education managers. (Deem, 1998: 67)

The hurdles to change appear large, however, there are also issues related to leadership and change that are potentially challenging. Leadership behaviour impacts organizational climate and motivation, which underpin performance and productivity (Barker, 2005). Also, leadership is one of the three catalytic variables in change (Smith, 2008) and the leadership needs certain qualities to lead the change. Six tenets of change that the leadership needs to possess to lead the change are: a research-based learning community, strategy, the ability to build relationships, communicate powerful messages, empower others, and finally have the courage to do what has to be done (ibid.). A leader's characteristics, or behaviour, appear to be paramount along with professional development which should be part of the fabric, and should be given priority in schools (Speck, 2008). Bryman (2007) lists eleven attributes of an effective leader's behaviour at a departmental level of which being considerate and initiating structure are considered to be two of them (Knight & Holen, 1985). If, as Amey (2006) notices, an upward influence in the hierarchy of a system is possible so departmental heads can help faculty heads, this becomes more poignant. However, to what extent can this principle cross cultural boundaries? Furthermore, a leader who is successful in implementing change in HE seems to be one who unifies through reconciliation, motivates towards unity, and ultimately change (Fullan & Scott, 2009). In short, a leader creates the optimum environment and conditions to facilitate others' performance, reducing hindrances so that one outcome is that the department's standing and reputation increases within and

beyond the institution's walls (Bryman, 2007). Needless to say ineffective leadership can result in damaging the commitment of colleagues (Bryman, 2007). Leithwood et al. found that leadership 'has very significant effects on the quality of school organisation and on pupil learning' (2008: 29) and can act as a catalyst for unleashing latent potential that already exists in an organisation.

In answer to the conundrum as to the role between leadership and school improvement Hallinger and Heck (2011: 22) state:

These results reinforce the long-standing empirical finding that leadership acts as a catalyst for school improvement, both by initiating change and shaping a coherent focus on learning in schools.

Leaders are considered pivotal to the functioning of an organization (Amey, 2006) as is their own development. This can be considered particularly important if a leader is seen to influence or motivate others towards certain goals (Bryman, 2007). Certainly leadership improvement is the start line for working towards increasing the potential for change within an institution (Thoonen et al., 2012) and through the process of improvement Hallinger and Heck (2011) state that leadership can spread into team attributes resulting in organizational property (Ogawa & Bossert, 1995), or becoming part of the organizational culture. This leads us to turn our attention to organizational culture and change.

Organizational Culture and Change

Tierney states 'the culture of an organization is grounded in the shared assumptions of individuals participating in the organization' (1988: 4). While external factors will influence an institution, the mindset of *the way things are done* that is infused in an institution is a powerful internal force that will determine the workings of the institution (Tierney, 1988). However, to what extent these transcend language and culture barriers in HU, and how these are transmitted to the NEI, could be a pertinent issue in this investigation. Tierney, (ibid), continues by stating that the more effective cultures are those that are strong and work together with organizational structures and the less effective cultures are those that are weaker, or are less united. Regarding cultural change in an institution Knight & Trowler (2000) argue it is unpredictable because it has to be collaborative.

Organizational culture appears to be able to facilitate change. This means that, in theory, it should be able to hinder change too. The concept of culture can facilitate solving administrative issues, although it is not a solution to poor administrative conduct. Kezar & Eckel (2002) recommend, before starting any process of change, conducting an audit on the organizational culture. This is because they believe that strategies that use a cultural approach for improvement, rather than a collaborative approach, yield thicker descriptions. However, there appear to be a number of other possible strategies for instigating change too. Another element to consider in organizational culture and change is how the change is measured, or how performance is measured. In class, instructors may use tests to measure student performance. Likewise across an institution, having accountability for professional standards of practice, or methods for reflection, can serve a dual purpose: they can assist instructors in examining and determining their own performance, and they can also be used

for measuring performance. It could be expected that there are also government initiated tools for measuring performance too. How all these tools are used and fed back into the cycle of improvement, can vary.

With change, or improvement, being a process, Chapman & Harris (2004) argue that different strategies are needed at different stages thus a one-glove-fits-all approach is inappropriate. One strategy is to use a conceptual framework which can help determine what factors are needed for change (Smith 2008). However, Hallinger and Heck (2011) identify patterns of practice that can be linked to a school's classification thus showing that each case does not have to be considered unique.

Either way, in an educational institution, changes might be found in processes and systems within the organisation. This brings us to the role of leadership within systems. Sammons et al. (1995) say that professional leadership, along with the processes, are very significant because they give the teachers and classrooms a parameter within which to work. If the institution is going to be a 'learning community' (Dimmock, 2005: 110) then all the members will be included, and following on from that leadership, influential. Emphasising this is the fact that leadership alone has little affect on students' learning outcomes (Barker, 2006) which indicates the importance of the cultural organisation and management. It appears that leadership can affect colleagues by creating opportunities that bring knowledge, and understanding (Caldwell & Spinks, 1998). It can also proliferate school improvement (Hallinger & Heck, 2011) giving it a respective part to play, and it can also 'arouse positive motivation' (Barker, 2005: 23). If leadership can proliferate school improvement then in theory it can also quell it, regardless of the organizational culture.

Leadership, Collaboration, Teamwork & Change

Leadership teams can play an important role in change as they can facilitate the distribution of leadership which in turn, Harris claims, 'has a direct impact on team development' (2010: 24). Hallinger and Heck's (2011) findings agree with this and they claim that a school's collective leadership reciprocally shapes school capacity. Indeed capacity, or potential, appears to be key. While working conditions, motivation and commitment have a certain degree of influence on altered practices of student learning and achievement, capacity appears to show the greatest influence on teachers changing classroom practices (Leithwood et al., 2008). Thus, developing teachers' capacities becomes more important.

Distributed leadership is reputed to extend beyond formal leadership or administrative roles indicating that this form of leadership is not confined to those with official leadership titles. Distributed leadership might appear quite attractive as Harris's (2010) study provides evidence for distributed leadership enhancing student outcomes, but it needs time to be cultivated. Furthermore, trust and confidence are needed. Core values and monitoring systems were also found among the distinctive features in nine high performing schools in the UK (Harris, 2010). However, Bush and Glover (2012) state there are four characteristics of high-performing leadership teams: having a commitment to distributed leadership, having two way communication, a clear focus on high standards, and internal coherence and unity. These four factors indicate that distributed leadership is something that needs to be desired and fostered. Hallinger and Heck (2011) note that leadership, through collaborative leadership, plays a key role in improvement. Furthermore, they claim stability and support are two key elements needed during change.

Morrison (1998: 88) discusses teamwork and its relevance to educational change and lists a number of advantages and disadvantages; teamwork can develop motivation and empowerment but, 'change, development and effectiveness comes from within, rather than from without' (ibid.). As change is often met with resistance (Kotter, 2012) teams can create a supportive climate (Morrison, 1998). Overall, Kotter (2012: 171) calls teamwork 'enormously helpful almost all the time' which emphasises its potential, and which leads us to an examination of teamwork.

Teamwork

The literature indicates there is a high chance of the strong Japanese collective work ethic, or mindset, emerging in the data of this study. Therefore, an us-and-them perception may also emerge from the data. It is possible the NEI feel grouped together in some way, even if only by default or isolation, and therefore this review includes literature related to working as part of a group.

Both external forces and internal dynamics influence how a group of people function. One external force is the culture of the organisation in which the team is found. Rubio-Andrés et al. state that, 'overall, corporate culture is the single largest predictor of the differences among the companies' (2014: 287) successful use of teams.' Developing a corporate culture conducive to supporting teamwork appears to require constant effort. Therefore, it seems teamwork has to be desired and pursued for it to flourish. How the team is put together is another influential factor (Austin & Baldwin, 1991). There are four hows that an effective collaborative team must work through: how members are chosen, how roles are defined, how guidelines are established, and how the collaboration should end (ibid.). Also, some

controversy has arisen from three areas: the misuse of power, professional identity being compromised, and integrity (ibid.).

Faculty collaboration has the potential to affect the way in which academia functions but it must also be fostered, and one way to do this is by involving others in 'decision making and faculty interaction' (Rosenholtz, 1989: 44). Collegiality can be a very attractive and encompasses a wide range of activities from staff-room chats to collaborative planning. Shulman's (1989) work notes benefits of collegiality including curriculum development and 'organizational health and effectiveness' (Hargreaves 1992: 81). However, there are barriers, as mutually shared values and goals are needed. If these cannot be established, there will be no starting point. Hargreaves notes other hindrances which include 'political control' (1992: 86) and 'systems in which decisions about curriculum and evaluation are highly controlled' (ibid.). There are five main features that squeeze collegiality making it contrived: when it is regulated by the administration of the institution, it is compulsory, participation is required, it occurs at a fixed time or place and when its outcomes are highly predictable (ibid.). Atwal & Caldwell (2006) found two factors that can hinder any teamwork: participants having differing concepts of what teamwork is and, members of the team having unequal levels of skills.

Playford et al. (2000), looked at goal setting within groups and found hindrances to effective teamwork came from external factors such as staff turnover, which the other team members had little or no influence over. This indicates that the relationships between members of the group and the skills of each person are of the utmost importance. This is substantiated by Ulloa & Adams' (2004) and Keen's (2003) findings. Keen points out that a team's

effectiveness can be put at jeopardy by 'any lack of dedication to the overall team effort' (2003: 4). This could explain why Japanese teamwork is so strong. Chua et al. (2012), looking at cross-cultural collaboration, found hindrances to team work such as anxiety, but that sharing personal information creates a foundation, upon which creative collaboration can be built. Chua et al. (ibid.) discovered that more cultural understanding leads to intercultural interaction which then fosters trust, upon which collaboration can be built.

Ulloa & Adams state, 'it is not just putting individuals together and assigning them a task' (2004: 145), 'specific required skills' (ibid.: 146) are needed to aid team effectiveness. Ulloa & Adams found: 'productive conflict resolution, mature communication, role clarity, accountable interdependence, goal clarification, common purpose and psychological safety' (ibid.: 145) as main elements necessary for effective teamwork. Those characteristics can be summed up in Keen's 'basic tenet' (2003: 41) which underpins team effectiveness which is: interdependency and its realisation.

The literature shows there are a number of facets that can influence groups of people working together. The culture of the organisation, the dynamics of the group and the leadership are the most evident. Finally, cultural ramifications are examined with multicultural teams, differences in national cultures, and cultural intelligence.

Multiculturalism & Teamwork

Although the NEI share the same language they are from four different nations and cultural diversity is a hallmark of MCTs (multicultural teams). While an MCT does not have to be

located in one place, it will have a common goal (Shokef & Erez, 2008). MCTs face challenges common to any team including interpersonal tensions which can be caused by a number of factors. One challenge is how to create an MCT that works effectively. CQ (cultural intelligence) has been found to effect performance (ibid.). The other most influential factor found to affect MCTs was global identity (ibid.). Schein, using the term 'cultural islands' (2010a: 389), states developing an understanding and empathy, as well as dialogue on 'how to get along better' (ibid.: 400), are important. He states issues including communication, misplaced boundaries due to cultural differences which can lead to further issues, plus rank and experience are 'essential component[s] of organizational leadership' (ibid.: 398-9) in cultural islands.

National Cultures & Cultural Intelligence

Two major differences between the English speaking nations and Japan in this study are apparent (Hofstede & Bond, 1984). One is that western nations have a low UA (uncertainty avoidance dimension) score which means they are prepared to take risks. Conversely, Japan has a high UA score which means the Japanese value security over risk. The second is long-term orientation (LT). Japan has a very high score which means it looks, thinks, and works towards long-term goals, whereas the western nations focus more on the quick short-term goals and rewards. This has already emerged in the literature in negotiating styles.

These differences could cause friction within the group and with the host culture. The number of NEI who lean towards their original culture versus the number who lean more towards the host culture, how norms are determined within the group, and the organizational

culture of this group could also cause contention. The possible effects of the differences in the cultural dimensions are outlined in Appendix 1.

Hofstede's dimensions are a useful guide for understanding cross-cultural differences. They provide a good foundation for understanding the cultures in this study, but the extent to which they are applicable to individuals remains ambiguous, and it might be better to take Livermore's stance of the dimensions being a 'useful guide' (2009: 104). As Ng et al., state, it was this inability to 'solve cross-cultural problems' (2012:30) that led to the conception of cultural intelligence (CQ).

Early & Ang define CQ as 'a person's capacity to adapt effectively to new cultural contexts' (2003: 59). They claim CQ has three facets: cognition, motivation, and behaviour. This became significant in 2007 when Ang provided a 'validated scale to assess individuals' CQ' (Ng et al., 2012: 26). Before this, interviewing was considered the 'most direct way of assessing how an individual functions in another culture' (Lee & Temper, 2003: 200). They state that, 'interviews are excellent sources of qualitative measurement' (ibid.: 201), but there are obvious disadvantages to interviews. Early & Mosakowski (2004) realised answers are highly subjective which can lead to conflict in the data. People's perceptions differ so data collected from two sources (a person living in the host culture and a person from the host culture) may have discrepancies. This means while NEIs believe they understand and have adapted to the Japanese culture, Japanese may not share this opinion.

As noted, CQ has been found to effect performance in multicultural teams (Ang & Van Dyne, 2008). Further results of Ng et al.'s study were threefold: CQ indirectly effects 'idea

sharing in intercultural ties through increasing affect-based trust' (2012: 41). Second, Cheng et al.'s (2008) findings were substantiated: 'only bicultural individuals with integrated cultural identities tend to be creative on tasks calling for knowledge that draws on both identities' (Chua & Morris, 2009: 11). Lastly, the findings agree with Hackman & Wageman (2005)'s, that building more personal relationships at an early stage when establishing a team, promotes idea sharing, without which the possibility for maximising diversity is hindered. There are some other definite advantages to CQ: it is learnable, its emphasis is on learned traits rather than personality traits (Livermore, 2011), and it can pave the way for strategically thinking people (Moua, 2011). In measuring CQ, the answers are subjective (Earley & Mosakowski, 2004), it is not just knowledge about another culture (Livermore, 2011) and finally, it is one of the two essential components that, Shokef & Erez state potentially increase a multicultural team's potential, with the other being a 'global identity' (2008: 177).

Livermore emphasises that CQ is not concerned with 'mastering all the specific information and behaviour needed for effectiveness in individual cultures' (2011: 33). Rather its focus is on 'developing an overall repertoire of understanding, skills, and behaviours for making sense of the barrage of cultures we encounter daily' (ibid.). However, it appears that Ang's instrument of measure fails to take into the account the host culture (Harris & Lievens, 2005). Mischel (2004: 234)'s findings also find it lacks a person-situation perspective. In practical terms this could mean one's communication may be effective in a different culture, but ineffective during teamwork in the host culture. This finding substantiates Smith's (1992) work. So, while CQ has its advantages and disadvantages, it reveals that working across cultures is not simply a matter of taking a set of skills and using it in another culture.

This study investigated the issues that are affecting the NEI, in HU, with the aim to offer suggestions for increasing institutional effectiveness among the NEI. Findings from the literature indicate how westerners have struggled to understand Japanese leadership which is pertinent to this investigation. How that underpins the organizational culture and change is also fundamental to this study. Coupled with differing interpretations of leadership, the role that organizational culture plays in change suggests that change in Japanese institutions could be a challenging process. In addition, the literature indicates a strong collective mentality in Japanese culture which avoids risk but could promote teamwork which the literature shows to be a powerful tool for improvement. This research could improve understanding of the impact of the cultural organization in this Japanese institution on the group of western instructors, and highlight potential elements necessary for improvement amongst the group which may be informative to others in similar situations. However, for potential for improvement to be unearthed, it is important to find out how the NEI perceive the current situation.

Considering the context of this study the overarching questions to be answered are:

What are the perceived enabling and constraining factors influencing institutional improvement amongst the NEI at Hokubetsu University?

And,

How do these perceived factors impact organizational culture, leadership and teamwork?

Methodology

In the literature I have substantiated how uniformity and commitment are key in Japanese leadership which is more of a mentality, rather than a system, and which has caused difficulties for westerners in comprehending it. This mindset, prevalent in attitudes and perceptions, will have far reaching effects into organizational culture, teamwork, and change. How this impacts the group of NEI and to what extent, and the ramifications of this, is complex. These factors, along with the initial prompt into the investigation dictated the methods used in this study.

A desire to understand and explore issues that were influencing my colleagues' actions, along with seeking to unearth what lay behind actions, thoughts, and behaviour, prompted this investigation. As a researcher, I wanted to understand the situation amongst the various backgrounds and cultures in this study, and be able to portray them honestly, and accurately. As an investigator, I needed to clarify and interpret what the participants were trying to communicate. The main aim of this study was to uncover what factors the participants perceive are enabling and constraining institutional improvement among them. Simultaneously, it was important to understand 'others' ideas and views' (Goldman, 2004: 158). Thus, the potential for differing opinions could emerge. Therefore, a 'holistic overview of the context' (Miles & Huberman, 1994: 6) was essential. 'Human life is experienced and constructed from a subjective perspective' (Briggs & Coleman, 2007: 27) which calls for catching the participants' perceptions (Punch, 2009), which in turn leads to qualitative research where participants have the freedom to express themselves in their own words, and explain situations from their own perspectives. Ultimately, the way for the

participants to share, as they desired, allowing for topics to arise as they talked, whilst clarifying certain points as situations unfolded, thus penetrating the 'meaning frames in which' (Briggs & Coleman, 2007: 27) the participants operate, was necessary.

Paradigm

Educational environments contain an immense array of pedagogic, political, economic, and social elements to examine as human nature is immensely complex (Cohen et al., 2007). Therefore, two people may interpret one incident from two different points of view and in two very different ways (Webster & Sell, 2007). The reasons for this are beyond the scope of this research, but it suffices to acknowledge that human opinions cannot be likened to cause and effect. Creswell (2013) uses the term postpositivist as a term representative of the worldview that has come since positivism, and states that postpositivists see the world as if there is a cause and effect with universal laws that govern us. Seeking to understand the world in which the participants are in, holds with the view that interpretivists have, which is that, 'individuals seek understanding of the world in which they live and work' (ibid.: 8). For a postpositivist, 'developing numeric measures of observations and studying the behaviour of individuals' (ibid.: 7) is foremost. However, this research is about the participants' thoughts, perceptions and observations. People may react to one stimulus in as many numbers of ways as there are internal and external variables, which then influence a response. Furthermore, positivists may start with a theory, but this investigation seeks to uncover theories. Therefore, the positivist paradigm does not fit this investigation.

This research seeks to explicate factors influencing institutional improvement from the participants' perspectives by seeking to understand participants' views about leadership,

change, teamwork and effectiveness within their workplace. Therefore, understanding the context holistically is paramount (Bush & Middlewood, 2013). Understanding the context, and having established 'a basic set of beliefs that guides action' (Guba, 1990: 17) next is the choice of approach.

Approach: Case Study

A qualitative, contextual study can employ several possible approaches such as ethnography, action research, or case study. With this investigation there are several factors that point towards a case study. One pertinent factor is the need to maintain the 'wholeness, unity and integrity' (Punch, 2009: 120) of the study. This study was too complex for surveys or experimental design as 'experimental data cannot tell...how human action fits into larger schemes' (Webster and Sell, 2007: 197). Also, case studies are useful as a 'form of enquiry, as an exploration of the unknown' (Bassegy, 2007: 142). In addition, this research takes place within one institution making a case study approach suitable (Bassegy, 2007). As Miles & Huberman (1994) state, a case study is a 'phenomenonoccurring in a bounded context' (Punch, 2009: 117). Furthermore, it allows for the investigation to take place 'in its natural context' (Bassegy, 2007). Finally, this study lies in the confines of time and space (Bassegy, 2007) as it investigates one group of people in one institution at a defined time. All these factors point to a case study approach.

Methods: Qualitative

Large scale investigations into the views and perceptions held by teachers have often employed questionnaires (Cooper et al., 1998). Nevertheless there are pertinent issues with questionnaires: they do not allow participants the freedom of response desired (Ribbins,

2007) in this study, if collected anonymously they cannot be double-checked later, there is no way to delve deeper into issues, and time to complete a questionnaire is limited (Bell, 2007) which limits data quality. Alternative methods of data collection were considered but due to limited researcher time a single method was employed. Furthermore, using interviews alone can avoid 'tensions that sometimes arise when a researcher uses multiple methods' (Seidman, 2012).

In seeking to disclose feelings and thoughts about experiences and events during the instructors' times at HU, and to not limit the quality and richness of the data collected, interviews, which yield 'rich and relevant data' (Ribbins, 2007: 207), were chosen. Ultimately, semi-structured interviews were chosen as they allow for the sequencing of the questions to be left to the discretion of the researcher (Coleman, 2012), a natural flow of conversations, a deeper penetration of certain areas, and the extraction of rich descriptions (Denzin & Ryan, 2007) as well as the way to clarify interpretations of events and circumstances. In collecting detailed, socially meaningful and rich data, interviews opened the way for a fuller understanding of the situation, providing a clear picture of how the participants perceived the situation which in turn, paved the way, for me as researcher, to open up and see the situation from the participants' viewpoints. Thus, due to the very nature of this investigation, and for all the reasons described above, the most appropriate way to obtain the data in the form needed would be in private interviews with each participant where confidentiality would be guaranteed.

Nevertheless, interviews have weaknesses; they take time, they have to be arranged, and the location can affect the interview (Cassell, 2009). To maximise the response rate for the

collection of good qualitative data two important factors were given consideration: the timing and procedure of data collection. The time allotted for collecting data was based on the academic calendar when the participants did not have classes, and to eliminate obstacles created by this timeframe the participants were given the choice of being interviewed in the institution, face-to-face, or by *Skype*, which is increasingly being used for interviewing (Bush, 2012).

While interviews using Skype should not be considered 'an easy option' (James & Busher, 2009: 6) in this research they were used to facilitate data collection as there were logistical mobility constraints thus adhering to Franklin's advice,

[i]nterviews conducted over the phone, Skype included, are perfectly legitimate particularly if time and resources are limited for a face-to-face appointment. (2012: 118)

One advantage to using Skype is it is non-threatening as participants can feel they are in a 'safe location' (Hanna, 2012: 241). Furthermore, Skype allows researchers and participants to participate in

an exchange relationship that is visible either through the use of video recording or one's own eyes, gestures, shrugs, winks, smiles, frowns, and verbal cues [that] are all a visible part of the process allowing for impression-management (Sullivan, 2012: 56)

and while there have been concerns over authenticity of online interactions, regardless of whether the interview is in person, or on-line,

[t]here is no sure way to judge...whether or not a person is being truthful about the information they are sharing regardless of the method of data collection. (Sullivan, 2012: 56)

Furthermore, Peterson points out, authenticity is socially constructed and therefore changing all of the time. He continues: 'issues of authenticity most often come into play when authenticity has been put in doubt' (2005: 1083). In this investigation there was no doubt. The participants were at ease, as mentioned below, to the extent that some talked for up to an hour on Skype possibly because as Sullivan points out,

the researcher and interviewee are participating in an exchange relationship that is visible either through the use of video recording or one's own eyes. (2012: 56)

However, this does not negate the researchers obligation to 'construct trustworthy knowledge' (Busher & James, 2009: 1). Busher & James suggest, to ensure the verification of online data 'as authentic' (2009: 79), using 'an ongoing reflexive process' (ibid.) approach. That said, in this investigation the data was treated equally rigorously regardless of collection method, and ultimately 'the authenticity of data collected in the online environment is no more problematic than in any other' (ibid.). Janghorban et al. conclude that, 'Skype offers an alternative or supplemental choice to researchers' (2014) and interviews by Skype

should be treated as a viable option to the researcher rather than as an alternative or secondary choice when face-to-face interviews cannot be achieved. (Deakin & Wakefield, 2013: 604)

as in this investigation.

Prior research raised some core questions (Greatbach, 2009). Along with these initial samples of data, research questions were also drawn from being researcher in the place of investigation. These questions, along with theoretical concepts (Burgess, 2002), the research literature and the research context (Hatch, 2002), were used to provide a basic framework from which a few, open-ended and straightforward questions were generated (ibid.) and then used during the research process (see Appendix 3).

Ethics

Following the University of Leicester's procedure for ethical approval the application was granted and the university's guidelines, and B.E.R.A guidelines, were adhered to. While 'there are codes of ethical and professional conduct for research' (Punch, 2009: 49) that must be adhered to, there are issues that are 'sometimes more acute in some qualitative approaches' (ibid.: 50) of which Punch lists eleven. The more pertinent to this study are addressed below.

There were a number of facets that had ramifications for the ethics of this investigation. Respecting people in case studies is pertinent (Bassey, 1999). The four questions that Bassey (1999: 77) puts forth (Appendix 4) were carefully considered and checked at each

appropriate stage of the investigation. As a result at the sixth stage, the matter of 'concealing the contributing individuals' (ibid.) was of particular concern due to the context of this investigation. Keeping harmony in the Japanese culture is of paramount importance (Black et al., 1999) as is putting one's personal opinions second to the company policy (Nakano, 1997). Furthermore, participants sharing stories of incidents involving other participants threatened confidentiality. In interviewing, the participants' anonymity as defined by Bell (2007) was not possible, which increased the desire to attain confidentiality, and the importance of voluntary participation.

With interviews being intrusive, and potentially leaving participants 'worse off at the end of a research intervention than when the research began' (Busher & James, 2007: 114), measures to prevent this were taken. The participants were all given androgynous pseudonyms and the gender of some participants was changed creating a 1:1 ratio men: women, which compromised the original gender distribution which was originally 13:1. Also, divulging the post held by each participant at the time of the interview could compromise confidentiality, therefore, this information was withheld. However, so as not to behead the data, positions that each participant had held over their time of working in the establishment was informative, and did not compromise confidentiality, so is shown in Table 1. Also, information regarding the posts, number of participants in that post, and time the posts have been held, is informative so is shown in Table 2.

A problem with interviews is the participants can begin to 'take greater ownership of the process of narrative construction' (Busher & James, 2007: 115). As the data was analysed, with an accurate portrayal being critical, discernment between well-thought-out complaints

and people bearing grudges was necessary. Complementary to this were other aspects to data handling. Permission was obtained from each participant to record the interview from which the transcripts were typed up by the researcher. The transcripts were sent to each participant for respondent validation (Scott & Morrison, 2006) which indicated that the participants were comfortable that what was written was a fair representation of the 'conversation with a purpose' (Burgess, 2002: 84). After receiving the validations in writing, the transcripts were prepared for analysis, which entailed all the place names and references to other establishments being given pseudonyms. The data was printed for analysis, and was treated as confidential.

Despite painstaking measures to protect the participants, Baez (2002: 53) argues that

harm is inherent to all research, and the uncertainty over whether any action will cause harm is a fact of all qualitative research.

One participant likened the interview to Schrödinger's cat which revealed the interview process did impact the participant. Malcolm effectively illustrates that ultimately those that are going to talk, 'will tell their story to anyone who will listen to it' (2011: 98). Regardless, the researcher must conduct the research in an ethical manner, and 'construct an ethical environment for the research' (Busher & James, 2007: 119).

Riddell (1989) points out there are a 'range of ethical problems [that can arise] concerning power relations which exist for a female researcher interviewing men' (Burgess, 2005: 80). However, as this investigation was carried out by a western woman of indeterminate status,

there was little risk of colleagues being overawed. Rather, the participants spoke freely giving sufficiently detailed descriptions. Being a female researcher was possibly less threatening to the predominantly male participants and possibly eased data collection (Seidman, 2012).

Data Collection.

Details of the study were given to all the native English instructors in a letter (Appendix 2), inviting them to participate in the survey. Fourteen of the fifteen instructors willingly volunteered. Responses were collected and dates for the interviews set by e-mail leaving a written record of dates and conditions agreed for each interview. A second letter detailing the questions (Appendix 3) was then sent to the participants giving them time to prepare their answers. At this juncture the interview location was decided.

Before the interviews were conducted the participants were reminded that the research was for academic purposes. Each participant was asked for their consent to record the interview, and during the interviews notes were typed for interview purposes. Each interview was recorded using the *voice memos* app on a disconnected iPhone to 'minimise intrusivity' (Ribbins, 2007: 207). Care was taken to use 'clear and unemotional wording' (Gorard, 2003: 112) and all the interviews closed with an invitation for the participant to ask questions (Basit, 2010). After each interview the data was transcribed, and to reduce interviewer bias, the transcripts were sent to each participant for respondent validation before analysis. A 'case record' (Bassey, 2007) was created and sound files and notes were archived after verification, and deleted after analysis. In total approximately 64,000 words were then prepared for analysis.

Authenticity

As case studies are a one-off event, reliability is 'an impractical concept' (Bassegy, 2007:194) because the interpretivist paradigm sees the world as a 'construct in which people understand reality in different ways' (Morrison, 2012: 20). Thus the interpretivist researcher understands that both the participants and the researcher are both a part of the matter under investigation and the researcher is not separate from it. Consequently the researcher may have an impact on the participants and visa versa (ibid.). As interviews elicit 'stories' and 'narratives' (Denzin, 2009: 151), care was taken to remind participants the purpose of the investigation and its recording, and to reconfirm that transcripts would be send for checking. Furthermore, questions guided interventions ensuring comparability between the interviews, and to maintain focus on the research.

As reliability and validity are primarily associated with positivist research, Bush (2012) argues that authenticity is more important for qualitative research, which then raises the issue of trustworthiness (Bassegy, 2007). Bassegy, (1999) details the eight points which Lincoln & Guba (1985) put forward for trustworthiness in case studies and these were used as guidelines. However, with informant feedback, Miles et al. (2013) point out that participants may not always agree with each other, nor the researcher, and this is to be expected in a site that is not conflict-free (ibid.: 310). For this reason, two participants who are no longer at the site were also chosen for critical feedback.

Despite measures being taken to increase trustworthiness, Yin states 'a research design is supposed to represent a logical set of statements' (2013: 45) that you can judge according to

'logical tests' (ibid.). Yin's four tests of construct validity, internal validity, external validity and reliability are discussed below.

Validity

Construct validity is achieved through 'correct operational measures' (Yin, 2013: 46) which include using multiple sources of data, establishing a chain of evidence and also having informant feedback. How this was handled has been covered above.

Internal validity, as defined by Yin (ibid.) was not sought in this investigation as it is 'not for descriptive or exploratory studies' (ibid.: 46). External validity, (ibid.) seeks to determine the generalizability of the study. The aim of this research is not to make generalisations applicable to other universities. Rather, by looking into one establishment, at one set of people at one time, the aim is the results of this investigation will be helpful to the participants and the institution, although the findings may be of interest to parties in similar contexts.

Yin's (2013) reliability is a test that allows another researcher to draw the same conclusions and findings of the investigation. Therefore a researcher must have transparent handling, documentation, and analysis of the data.

It is possible that a different researcher with a different point of view may have a differing interpretation of the data collected through the interviews in this investigation, and this 'is how it should be' (Denzin, 2009: 154). It can also be argued that the depth of data each participant gave can be influenced by the depth of relationship with the researcher as 'social

forces of class ... impose themselves on the interviews' (Seidman 2012: 97). For some participants this might be true, however possibly these relationships were catalysts for obtaining thick, rich descriptions. Regardless, Malcolm points out one might expect more wariness from the interviewee, but, 'childish trust and impetuosity are far more common' (2011: 32). In this study each participant was free to answer the questions to the extent they desired, but interviewing skill can be learned (Ribbins, 2007), and possessing some from professional training may have facilitated data collection.

Positionality

With one researcher conducting all the interviews this was a constant which reduced variables that arise from having a number of interviewers. This may increase interviewer bias (Woodside, 2010). Unacknowledged, and unreflective researcher bias is a potential threat to validity (Johnson & Christensen, 2010). Ways to combat this can be through reflexivity on the part of the researcher, or negative-case sampling (ibid.). In this investigation, interpretive validity, which Johnson and Christensen define as, 'portraying accurately the meanings attached by participants to what is being studied' (2010: 300) was employed. This was achieved by being employed in the same milieu that I researched, which gave me a certain understanding of the context. Furthermore, having worked in the Japanese culture for approximately 20 years and having fluent Japanese language skills, this deepened my understanding of the context.

To reduce bias member checking of all the transcripts was used. The interviews were transcribed verbatim and checked by each participant for inaccuracies, or lack of clarity. In using the direct quotes from the interviews the participants' worlds are opened up to the

reader directly allowing the readers to 'experience for themselves the participants' perspectives' (Johnson & Christensen, 2010: 302). As a novice researcher, there were times when the interviewee sought agreement or justification of thoughts or actions but 'my only obligation from the beginning was to tell the truth' (Malcolm, 2011: 25). The truth, in each participant's view, was what the researcher trusts the interviewee to share, and all the data was treated as a fair representation of 'all view points' (Thorsen, 2008).

Triangulation

Triangulation is an issue with research that relies on interviews alone (Guba & Lincoln, 1981) and adds breadth and depth of understanding (Mills et al., 2009). From Denzin's (1989) initial four types of triangulation, six are now used, which are: data source, investigator, theory, methodological, data type, and analysis triangulation (Mills et al., 2009). Data source triangulation (Chow, 2008) was utilised by interviewing tenured, limited-term contract, and part-time NEI. With fourteen participants, there was enough correlation between the data to establish evidence. Saturation, as described by Kvale (2007) was also apparent.

Data Analysis

Qualitative data analysis methods need to be 'systematic, disciplined...transparent and described' (Punch, 2009: 171). Therefore, in this investigation, before analysis, the data was rigorously checked for references to other people and places, all of which were given pseudonyms as previously mentioned. Denscombe's (2010) advice was followed to prepare the data for analysis; the data format was unified, spaces edited in for notes and memos, each piece of raw data given a name, and back-up files made of all the original transcripts.

The three 'concurrent streams' (Punch, 2009: 174) in the Miles and Huberman framework were followed for analysis. The summarizing, coding and memo taking of data was done by hand. Data display included charts by theme and by contrast and clustered data (Punch, 2009). Thus, data reduction, through analytic choice which lead to coding, organising themes, and discarding irrelevant data (Miles & Huberman, 1994), honed down patterns and themes which exposed variables and their relations. From the themes' variables and relations, theories were generated which were tested and confirmed against the data using the literature. This gave interpretation and explanation of factors and the impact on the themes that had been highlighted through the literature, which answered the research questions (ibid.).

Analysis

This case study seeks to illuminate factors effecting institutional improvement in the eyes of fourteen native English instructors (NEI) employed in HU at the time of investigation. The literature indicates possible factors that contribute to, and hamper, institutional improvement which may be due to a number of causes including the organisational culture within the university. Other potential causes include cultural differences between the instructors and the Japanese environment, the leadership in the university, and, or possibly teamwork. Unearthing what hindrances exist, and determining what actions are advisable could reduce the barriers to institutional improvement, opening the way to working towards improved effectiveness.

The research questions, which were framed from the initial samples of data and from being researcher in the place of investigation, are:

What are the perceived enabling and constraining factors influencing institutional improvement amongst the NEI at Hokubetsu University?

And:

How do these perceived factors impact organizational culture, leadership and teamwork?

This analysis first presents, and then discusses, the data gathered for this investigation in relation to the research. The participants are listed (in alphabetical order of their pseudonyms) in the table below which also shows the gender allotted to each pseudonym

and the method of the interview chosen by the participant. Positions held in the university are:

L/C: Limited Contract, or 'contract-teachers', who are full-time, non-tenured staff employed full-time on a limited contract for a maximum period of five years (also referred to, in the data as 'full-time').

P/T: Part-time teacher

T: Tenured, also referred to, in the data as 'full-time'.

Table 1: Participants

No.	Name	Gender assigned	Interview method	Interview Date	Position(s) Held
1	Alex	Female	face-to-face	4th February 2013	L/C & P/T
2	Brett	Male	face-to-face	4th February 2013	L/C & P/T
3	Dee	Female	Skype	4th April 2013	L/C & P/T
4	Francis	Female	face-to-face	1st February 2013	P/T
5	Glen	Male	Skype	6th March 2013	L/C
6	Jules	Male	face-to-face	4th February 2013	P/T & T
7	Kim	Female	Skype	1st March 2013	P/T
8	Lee	Male	face-to-face	8th April 2013	P/T
9	Lesley	Male	Skype	8th March 2013	P/T
10	Marty	Female	face-to-face	1st February 2013	T
11	Nat	Male	Skype	1st March 2013	P/T
12	Noel	Male	face-to-face	28th March 2013	P/T
13	Pat	Female	Skype	5th March 2013	P/T
14	Sam	Female	Skype	14th March 2013	P/T

(Some participants have held more than one type of position.)

Table 2: Distribution of Participants & Posts

Post Held in HU	No of Participants	Post Held (years)
Tenure	2	15 - 28
Full-Time Limited Contract	3	2 - 4
Part time	9	1 - 23

Presentation of Findings

The presentation of the data is divided into three parts. The data on institutional improvement is presented first; the data on impediments comes next; last is the data on reducing impediments to improvement.

What factors are contributing to institutional improvement?

The data is displayed under the key themes from the literature: organisational culture, leadership and teamwork, in this order.

Organisational Culture

From the data, relating to organisational culture, are efficiency, and decision making and change. Six of the fourteen participants commented favourably on the efficiency of the administration within the university. A 'good admin team' (Alex) conveys the general idea. With work being done 'promptly' and 'well' (Dee) and staff are described as being 'cooperative' and 'efficient' (Kim). HU is described as a very 'democratic organisation'

which depends on 'group decision making' (Jules), and if one is sensitive to the cycles of the processes which involve decision making, change is achievable (ibid.). Power bases are opaque (Marty), and policies are transparent being dictated to everybody by the procedures and policies which are detailed in a 'big black book' (Jules). Thus it appears the whole university runs on committees and 'group based leadership' (Jules). 'The whole university runs by consensus' (Alex).

Leadership

Some participants regard 'the leadership' as doing well, 'putting a lot of effort into curriculum development' (Pat, Kim), helping out (Nat), having initiated some great programmes in the university (Sam), trying to change things (Glen), 'acting as a mediator' (Francis), and pointing people in the 'right direction' as well as 'doing their job well' (Lesley). It seems the tenured staff have 'tightened up the ship' (Pat) and have tried to increase coordination, 'and get more cohesion amongst the content of people's courses' (Kim). Kim can see 'how that can be useful for the university as a whole.' Text book or curricula changes have also been made (Pat). Through these types of developments respect is earned (Sam).

Teamwork

The data gives a glimpse that shows evidence of both teamwork and autonomy. Syllabus planning (Noel), being 'paired up' to use the same text book (Lee) and teaching classes that are like 'one giant class divided into three different personalities' (Nat) along with the feeling of being part of a team (Sam) were mentioned. Sharing files is facilitated by the university's Moodle site where there is a 'sharing cart' (Alex). Exactly half of the

participants made positive reference to having autonomy in the classroom. The teachers have had independence and freedom to design their own classes and run everything themselves (Lesley) which has enabled the use of their own materials (Francis) ultimately letting everyone do what they want (Brett) which has given personal satisfaction (Kim). Teachers have become accustomed to this system (Marty), not having to coordinate with other teachers (Pat). 'The teacher can determine what they want to do in the class for all of the class' (Lee).

Having seen the data pertaining to the factors contributing to improvement among the NEI in HU, the data pertaining to the impediments towards improvement among the group are now presented. The data for this section is, again, organised by organisational culture, leadership, teamwork and cultural differences, with sub-themes within each.

What factors are impeding institutional improvement?

Organisational Culture

Within the organisational culture of HU two principal hindrances emerged: a lack of clarity, and change within the university. Clarity is presented first.

Ten of the fourteen participants lamented over various aspects of vagueness in relation to their jobs. Three main areas lacking clarity that surfaced are: the curriculum (two participants), their job as a teacher (three participants), and general over-arching areas (eight participants) which are detailed below.

For Lesley, he is unsure of what his 'new role is, exactly, with the next system'. He states that from the new academic year there will be 'new proficiency tests' and 'different changes' including being 'paired off with another teacher' and having to 'coordinate' classes. Whilst keeping an optimistic tone, he expressed doubt about the new academic year. How classes will be coordinated, or what the pairing off involves, is unclear to him. For Pat the conundrum lies with a test that is being used for 'placement purposes' and making it part of the teacher's grade. 'I'm not sure how to do that' (Pat).

With their teaching role three participants expressed their feelings about a lack of information.

This has surprised me at university....[I] have never been given anything ... printed in English, that tells me what my job is, what I am supposed to do, what facilities are available ... it's kind of *somewhere*. (Noel)

The vagueness extends into the classroom,

I'll plan my own lessons and my own curriculum, but sometimes I did not know the goal or, what do you want them to get out of this? (Sam)

Not only pertinent issues seem ambiguous:

Even the little I did not know. There were so many things I discovered... A lot of stuff is not forthcoming. (Sam)

She thinks, 'They try to keep that secret'.

While a lack of information about teaching roles and curricula was expressed by four of the participants, a general lack of clarity was expressed by over half. This includes knowing 'who is who' (Alex, Noel), information about the students, for example what field they are majoring in (Marty) or what level they are (Sam), and pertinent information such as the location of the part-time teachers' room (Marty). Alex pointed out that there was 'a lack of coordination, communication.' As the mission statement was not pointed out to her, she 'kind of operated under' her 'own mission statement'. The lack of 'direction and focus' along with there being 'no opportunity for discussion for feedback' all add to Alex's frustrations. 'Nobody knows who to report to,' she continued. 'We don't have an organisational chart'. Brett describes this as being in 'a grey zone.'

This lack of clarity extends further. Alex give details: the NEI all appear to be a part of the Faculty of Humanities, and a part of the department

which is kind of the English section of the department, which is where the foreign staff are that teach English as a foreign language. We have English teaching staff, within the Faculty of Humanities... Some are in the English Department too which is a separate department, and there is a lot of cross over. So, I think... I guess, we are under the Faculty of Humanities, but what we do is being directed by the English Department.

The result of this is not knowing who 'we actually report to' (Sam). Marty, however, has worked it out and reveals the situation. Bar the tenured staff all the other NEI are working

for 'General Education' which does not belong to any department. The tenured staff belong to the English Department where 'their primary duties' lie, but they may teach classes for other departments.

The contract teachers work for General Education. However, ... [they] are seconded for some classes for the English [Department].

The part-time teachers work for General Education but their 'primary duties' are 'to teach any department.' To add to this *mélange*, Marty added, 'It's getting more fluid.' However, this lack of clarity is not exclusive to the NEI:

Japanese colleagues acclimatise themselves more quickly but I have talked to Japanese colleagues, who even after seven years, were working out the rather Byzantine system between departments. (Marty)

A lack of clarity and transparency is also evident in the procedures for recruitment. Table 3, below, illustrates that the large majority got their current job through a contact and only one person was offered a position in response to an advertisement. While the university has a vetting system for tenured and contract teachers, the hiring for part-time teachers is less defined. One participant commented, "They contacted me when they needed someone... [there is] no proper recruitment process."

Table 3: Recruitment Procedures

Job Obtained through Advertisement	1
Job Obtained through a contact	13

With this evident lack of clarity, and information, surfacing in a number of areas communication becomes pertinent. Only one teacher expresses appreciation about the way Japanese hold meetings and make decisions. No one else seems to share this appreciation. 'Japanese communication, which does not work between Japanese administration and non-Japanese natives' (Nat) was a source of frustration and was viewed as 'wishy washy' and 'fuzzy' (Alex).

It is hard to 'change things' in the university (Glen, Marty). One of the reasons that change is difficult to implement is due to the way decisions are made (Marty) which Alex sees as 'a kind of reflection of Japan as a whole.' In the current system, if an idea is not accepted by your colleagues, it can be quickly rejected. This allows for any ideas that might be perceived by your colleagues as 'too radical' (Marty) to be eradicated. Alternatively suggestions can fall on 'deaf ears' (Jules). Japan is a 'consensus-based society' (Alex) and the university lacks a chancellor to give it vision; it is like a 'boat without a captain' (ibid.). In one (Japanese) meeting the discussion in the meeting 'did not focus, at all, on any of the proposals ... but on the appropriate procedures'(Marty).

Part of the resistance to change is due to job security amongst the Japanese staff (Marty). While people desire a 'dynamic English Department' people are not prepared to change

(ibid.). 'This reluctance to change is very characteristic of Japanese culture' (ibid.). At least it appears to be a 'top-down scenario, and it's not going to change' (ibid.). It took ten years to 'introduce a listening component into the entrance test' (ibid.). One way to overcome the resistance to change, may lie in 'writing reports' and 'justifying the change' (Jules).

Jules defines two types of culture operating in the university: an academic culture and bureaucratic culture, the latter is 'after efficiency' and avoids sudden change. A lack of change was commented on (Noel, Alex) as 'change takes time' (Alex). Changing 'everything you see needing to be changed [is] hard' (Jules) and it appears there are many problems that are noticeable when the curriculum is looked at as a whole. (Jules)

However, there were some changes noted. The introduction of technology in the classroom with blended classrooms and Moodle was the most noted change (Brett, Dee, Jules, Lesley). Student related changes included a decline in student numbers (Francis, Marty), and the increase of diversity in the level of students (Pat, Marty). 'Some departments stopped making English compulsory for second year students' (Francis). Administration changes within the university included 'departmental policy changes' (Kim, Jules) and procedures on taking student attendance (Pat). Brett considers no changes are needed, but Marty feels the university has failed to respond to current social trends. Other changes mentioned include a reduction in pay (Lee), new buildings (Marty, Pat), change of the contract teachers (Nat), introduction of placement tests (Jules), and increased collaboration amongst the foreign English teachers (Jules, Marty). There were no comments relating to any university, or Ministry of Education, led changes in either policy, benchmarks or standards required for students to reach, or teachers to teach to.

Leadership

For this section on leadership the data refers to leadership within the institution, and leadership over the NEI. Data on these two types of leadership are presented one after the other.

The leadership within HU appears somewhat nebulous. 'What leadership?' questions Noel who wonders whether 'it might be partly to do with the way things are structured.' Pat comments, '[The Japanese teachers] are the leaders of the department, right? I don't know their names... I have no idea if I have met [them].' Jules thinks leadership depends upon the 'effort of the teacher' and 'convincing your colleagues of a plan' while Brett thinks that leadership by definition means there are followers, but perceives there are none. Nine participants clearly state they perceive the 'tenured staff' as the leadership and reasons given include because they were 'the main contact person' (Lee), presented themselves as 'the boss' (Glen), or have been 'extremely helpful' (Nat). Nevertheless, this does not appear to be the case. It seems one NEI perceives the tenured staff as 'not our boss' but a 'lifeline' (Sam). More data sheds light on the authority of the tenured staff:

we actually have no authority over the contracted teachers or the part-time teachers. Any authority we have we have taken ourselves. In the hierarchy of the university we are not in a position of authority and what we have done in relation to the [native] teachers is what we have done on our own initiative. (Marty)

So, without being officially given authority, but taking a position of leadership over the other NEI, data about leadership over the NEI emerges.

While the tenured staff are 'trying to do a good job' (Lesley), there are also a number of concerns voiced. There appears to be a lack of direction, the NEI 'all have different ways of going about achieving the goals' (Alex) and it seems there is some focus lacking (Alex). One question is whether the leadership has 'the leadership skills that are needed to bring a team together' (Noel). Until now it seems that the teachers 'have gone through a number of changes [that] seem to occur very fast, without any forethought' (Glen). It appears decisions are made with the exclusion of some teachers, even though these decisions could have an impact on their classes. 'It was introduced like this is what we are going to do' and consequently there was a lot of 'arguing and push back', and decisions are made 'among a few people and announced' (Glen). However, there appear to be areas that need working on, 'there is no attempt to make sure the grades reflect [whether the students are a] higher or lower level' (Pat).

Furthermore, 'people are scared of losing their jobs' (Glen) and it appears some 'are under pressure to perform and take on a syllabus they that are not happy with' (Alex) and it was because of this that one teacher 'move[d] on' (Francis). Unnecessary stress between teachers was caused when assigning classes. 'I was supposed to take a bunch of' another teacher's lessons (Sam). That other teacher '*loved* that lesson' (ibid.). The other teacher was very upset (ibid.). 'There was all this talk back and forth' and in the end the teacher was able to keep the class (ibid.).

It seems 'someone [is] using their power to get people to do what he wants them to do' (Glen) and there are noticeably 'stressed faces' (Kim). There were comments about teachers having 'no choice if they want to remain working here or not' and there being,

'definitely a top-down form of corporate bullying; do this or you don't have a job' (Alex). It appears some teachers have learned to 'distrust' one of the tenured teachers. 'You don't *trick* people into things' (Glen). The interpretation is that the leadership style is 'immature' (Noel).

Stories of incidents stem back to when some of the contract teachers first started teaching in HU and 'where they felt it is better to be an island and focus on what they are doing.' There were 'bad experiences'(Alex). As a result some were 'turned off' this leader (Glen). Other incidents lead to feelings of being 'deceived' and feeling 'very suspicious' (Glen). Part-time teachers 'know they could lose their job' (Glen) and short-term gains are traded for a 'long-term environment' where the teaching and students could be impacted in a negative way. 'It's controlling' (Glen) and the full-time teachers have 'learned to distrust' this teacher (Sam).

Teamwork

There is conflicting data about teamwork with evidence of both teamwork and autonomy. With teamwork concerns and hindrances were voiced. The hindrances are presented first.

The participants are aware of obstacles preventing teamwork. Barriers exist that have taken 'years and years and years to build' (Alex). The atmosphere of being all 'individuals and we do what we want' (Noel) and the teachers enjoying it (Sam, Kim) along with a lack of previous experience of teamwork at HU (Lesley, Dee, Francis) were all mentioned. Further obstacles voiced include no 'common room' for 'interaction' with other teachers (Alex) which reiterates the need and desire for a place for teachers to casually sit and talk about

ideas (Marty, Glen, Noel) and which would be instrumental in bringing about 'situations where it is ...more conducive' for 'teamwork and collaboration' to take place 'naturally' (Sam). Feelings of isolation (Marty) as 'everyone is locked in their own office ... worried' create suspicion of one another (Alex). Part-time and full-time teachers may not be thought to have equal 'value' (Noel), but the paradox may be in how to get part-time teachers more involved (Glen). Whether the tenured staff have what is needed to bring a team together is also a concern (Noel, Glen). Finally, a lack of trust (Glen, Alex, Sam) between fellow native English teachers was found due to experiences which have been detailed above.

While there is evidence that teamwork exists, not everyone is involved, and NEI hear others talking about having to 'coordinate with other teachers' but not being directly involved (Pat). The flip side is autonomy is also appreciated. At one point here were no teams, 'every teacher had a different book' (Dee) and the teachers had a 'sheet of verbs and nouns' students were to know before moving into the second year. That all changed with teachers using the same book, 'with more technology,' and more communication between teachers. Added to this are the concerns about teamwork and how it could effect the classroom.

Some of the participants shared concerns about limitations of teamwork. To be a part of a team you need to desire it, and be happy with that (Sam, Marty) but it seems the teachers 'have to do team teaching and all have to use two or three different text books' (Francis). A problem can also be the teamwork is influenced by the other members of the team (Sam, Jules) which means with a big team it is harder to find a 'meeting point' that satisfies everyone (Francis). Not wanting to use a text, or use an evaluation system, they 'are not

happy with' is a concern (Marty), but moreover it appears 'someone might be trying to create collaboration [or] teamwork' when the concept is not fully grasped (Noel). To some, teamwork is new (Francis).

Cultural Influences

A divide between these two groups of teachers is apparent. The NEI are said to 'have little respect for the Japanese teachers' (Sam) and the stereotypical image is that Japanese teachers 'don't speak English'. The apparent image Japanese colleagues have of the NEI is they play games so students 'don't learn any English of academic value' (ibid.). The extent to which these stereotypes are true, and apply to HU, is unclear from the data; this is the only mention of such opinions. However, 'collaboration between western, foreign, teachers and Japanese teachers, [is] unfortunately' lacking (Sam).

The students' attitudes towards their studies is unfathomable to the participants of whom over half commented. The lack of English ability (Lesley) or the low level of some students (Marty, Noel, Glen) is one source. Lesley and Noel believe the students are doing their best whereas Marty puts it down to a 'lack of interest' and Sam is frustrated by the 'lack of logic,'

I came to realise that ... they have been coddled and pushed through the system for so long that they may not have that within them.

'Strenuous efforts' were made for this type of student (Marty). 'We offered personal assistance ... all kinds of strategies. They ... drop out' (ibid.).

Noel offers insight into the lack of interest and motivation:

Maybe they don't belong at university. They are very poorly prepared for Uni education ... maybe not that highly motivated and not that academic.

Francis thinks the 'relaxed education system' could be to blame. Putting the reasons aside, Lee finds students 'blowing him off' or 'not connecting' frustrating. This apparent lack of interest is shared by Francis' experience of students arriving late which ultimately leads to losing '15 mins at the start of class'.

Within the parameters of teamwork the numerous obstacles hindering teamwork have surfaced. Following on is what the participants desire, or see, is necessary for teamwork, and what would reduce obstacles to institutional improvement amongst the participants.

What would reduce the impediments to institutional improvement?

As above, the data is presented by the themes of organisational culture, including a comparison to other universities, leadership, teamwork and cultural issues.

Organisational Culture

While 'vision is lacking' the president of the university also changes 'every two years' (Alex) so commitment and long-term goals are questioned. There is a lack of opportunity 'for discussion' and 'feedback' (ibid.). The president changing every two years causes concern, 'the [external] environment is changing' and 'decisions need to be made fairly quickly nowadays' (Alex). Additionally, change takes time but the contract teachers

are 'only here for a short while' and Alex questions 'is it worth the effort?'. There was no direct question, but nine of the participants shared other models they have experienced at other local universities (Appendix 4).

Leadership

Four of the participants talked about a leadership style they like. Francis thinks that most teachers would like to work under a leader who 'gives free rein to the teachers,' trusts them to do a good job, leaving them to select their own text, and teach using their 'own style,' but also someone who is 'accessible for advice and help'. Lesley's comments confirm this, 'if you hire a good person give them the leeway to do a good job'. A good leader points people 'in the right direction' (ibid.). However, Glen is happier if tenured staff make the large decisions, e.g. curriculum guidelines and the textbook, but leaves the nitty gritty, eg. evaluation, teaching style and methodology, up to the individual teacher. Making decisions through discussion, though, is another suggestion (Marty).

Teamwork

Sam talks about three types of people: 'There are people who come and cause disruption'. These people alienate some people and people eventually drift further apart. Then there are people who just do the bare minimum, 'almost a ghost entity, just doing as much as they need.' They do not contribute to the greater whole. Finally, 'there are people who come into an organisation who bring people together.'

Sam also talks about how important it is for all parties to be flexible. 'You need to be willing to work on a team.' However, it seems that not all are willing to bend, '[They] pushed it

through'. 'Vision is not bad, and if you gave people the option' this might be a healthy way to proceed (Sam). Wavering in opinion, 'maybe you do need to force them, but maybe it would be better if it was ... from the English Department' (Sam).

Another observation about teachers is they tend to be opinionated, good speakers, but poor listeners (Marty). Attempts in the past to bring more cohesion amongst the NEI have only ended in failures. Being accustomed to autonomy in the classroom is at one end, whilst at the other is seeing the need for some collaboration and cooperation. The question is how to strike this balance. Marty thinks that 'negotiation and discussion' is a good way to proceed. Fortunately, on the whole teachers are 'friendly and approachable' but when a stubborn teacher says 'my way is the only way and the best way' then problems arise (ibid.).

'Respect is important' and so is 'feeling part of a team' (Sam). The lack of mutual respect creates 'tension and negativity' (Sam).

I think collaboration, working together, everyone has to be on the same level playing field, together, and number one is trusting each other. That's important. (Alex)

Lesley appreciates what the tenured staff are trying to do at HU, 'if I was the boss ... I would have everyone on the same text book.'

The style of current leadership appears to be 'do this whether you like it or not' (Sam) and 'this is a team! We are going together to the breach!' (Noel). Trying for consensus, listening to voices of the people under you so you 'feel you are part of a team' are all ingredients that

are needed. The leadership would be 'pushing' (Sam) which could lead to 'entrenchment' (Marty) and could make people 'negative' (Sam). Possibly 'too much freedom' (Sam) was hampering pulling people together. There is no kind of unified programme despite over five years of working to achieve one (Sam).

Collaboration should be natural. Good teachers make it happen...you can't force collaboration, it's not successful. You can lead people ... (ibid.)

and provide environments conducive to collaboration, 'like [for] plants you provide nutrition' (ibid.), but it appears to be lacking.

However, the lack of interaction amongst the NEI is due to a number of causes. The annual March meeting is the only time during the year that Pat sees the other NEI, other than that, it seems their paths do not cross. That meeting 'is conducive to creating collaboration' (Sam) and Kim has 'picked up a lot' at them. However, there are also monthly meetings, but it seems that 'more purposeful meetings' (Alex) are needed so that 'it is not just a chat for two hours about nothing so we achieve nothing' (ibid.). A Japanese teacher does their 'attendance thing' and leaves (Sam), and some of the foreign teachers 'don't want to be there either' (ibid). One problem is 'moderation is lacking' and time is lost 'talking about what kind of movies you have seen' (ibid.). It seems 'they have to have a meeting so somebody quickly makes up an agenda' (Noel). Before purposeful meetings can be achieved 'we need to wipe the slate clean and start working on building up trusting working relationship[s]' (Alex).

Added to these issues are logistics. Alex points out, there is 'no common room ... to discuss things', 'where you can have your lunch, a cup of coffee,' where the 'staff mail boxes' and a 'photocopier' are, a 'work room and a meeting room all combined' where staff would have to go to do things, and where there would be 'incentive to chat' that would promote deeper relationships. The lack of a shared lounge, seems central. In such an environment sharing 'just seems to happen more easily' (Kim). Certainly Noel sees the benefit of having 'unstructured chat[s].' 'The unstructured spending time is very helpful' (ibid.). Ultimately 'we [native] teachers should be in one open plan office...with the part-time teachers' (Marty).

Cultural Influences

There is a lack of interaction between the Japanese teachers and the native teachers of English at HU. One step would be 'to be more involved with the [Japanese] teachers' (Alex). There were no ideas in the data of how this could be achieved.

Discussion

A number of factors enabling and constraining institutional improvement amongst the NEI, which are impacting the organisational culture, leadership and teamwork, is revealed by the data. The aim of this investigation is that, by illuminating the factors mentioned above, areas conducive to supporting the instructors might be strengthened, and areas of particular concern might be re-examined with the aim of reducing them. These factors are now discussed in light of past research.

Factors enabling institutional improvement among the NEI.

There are a number of factors contributing to institutional improvement which include the operational culture, the leadership and teamwork. These are discussed below.

Organisational Culture

A supportive working environment (Leithwood et al., 2008) is found in the data with regards to the operational culture, and with leadership and teamwork. Also, there is evidence of the executive culture (Schein, 2010b) being efficiently managed by 'cooperative' and 'efficient' staff which supports the instructors in their teaching role. Furthermore, it appears processes within HU are based on 'group decision making' which, in theory, opens the way for all ideas and voices to be heard.

Leadership & Teamwork

Evidence of team development through leadership (Harris, 2010) was found with half the participants expressing gratitude about how the tenured NEI leadership are helping, are

involved in supporting the part-time NEI, and are making an effort to 'tighten the ship'. Furthermore, they are very supportive towards other NEI by being 'extremely helpful', 'initiating great programmes', 'acting as a mediator', giving guidance, in doing their own job well, and acting as a role model that others can have confidence in. They have also made an effort to improve the curriculum. Teamwork is desired and facilitated by systems, such as the institution's Moodle site, as well as by those with a desire to work together. The NEI also desire to work together, and with the Japanese faculty.

There is clear evidence of factors facilitating institutional improvement amongst the NEI, yet, despite the support and efficiency expressed, a number of factors are creating barriers, and concerns.

Factors constraining & how to improve institutional improvement among the NEI

The hindrances to institutional improvement among the instructors are examined pertaining to the following areas: organisational culture, leadership, teamwork and cultural differences.

Organisational Culture

Schein (2010b) explains, of the three cultures in an organisation the operator culture is likened to the academic staff in a university. Underpinning the success of the operator culture are communication, trust and teamwork (ibid.). The data shows there are a number of factors that surface which include the systems and their alignment, communication within the organisation, decision making, and teamwork, which are examined. Decision making is discussed before communication.

Evidence of lengthy decision making processes where procedures, rather than issues at hand, surfaces in the data. This demonstrates the focus is on the process rather than the task. The university being run by 'consensus' indicates evidence of the ringi system (Lincoln and Kalleberg, 1990) which intensifies the importance of communication within the organisation (Smith, 1992). A lack of communication between hierarchy and community surfaces in the data. For the most part it appears the part-time NEI are not privy to the hierarchical structure of the system. Information not being communicated to the part-time NEI indicates barriers existing in the organisational culture, possibly due to a lack of infrastructure, or support. Indications of sub-cultures that Smith (1992) refers to, also appear. Why a department dropped compulsory English classes not being communicated accentuates the indication of sub-cultures, communication barriers, compartmentalisation, lack of relationship, and focus being on the department rather than the university as a whole. The NEI find themselves in a 'grey zone', not being a part of any department, which creates increased hindrances to creating relationships between the NEI and other departments or faculties. This again points to a lack of alignment between the cultures within the institution (Schein, 2010b). This signals community being outweighed (ibid.), misalignment of cultures within the organisation, and elements of disjointed functionality, although further research is needed to substantiate this. Organisational focus, clear goals, and a well communicated mission with explicit ways to clear outcomes are all lacking.

Information not being communicated has far reaching ramifications. The NEI do not comprehend where they are placed in the context of the institution and there is no organisational chart, no job description, and concerns over a general lack of clarity that extend as far as the curriculum and jobs cause deep, long-reaching effects. Remarks

expressing of a lack of 'place', or efforts being appreciated within the institution, have resulted in a loss of motivation, and the participants talked of other systems and courses in other universities; some of which could be seen as solutions to the current situation at HU (see Appendix 4). With complexities in the curriculum causing concern, participants are seeking, and have ideas about, alternative frameworks within which to work. However, with only top-down communication systems there seems to be little way for their voices to be heard. With this backdrop change within organisational culture is now examined.

If, as Tierney (1988) claims, shared assumptions create the foundation of the culture of an organisation, then what shared assumptions are there in HU? The data shows that not all the NEI feel included, indicating an absence of Dimmock's 'learning community' (2005: 110). Tierney (1988) also claims that less united cultures are weaker, and the data indicates this exists in HU which ultimately reduces effectiveness (ibid). Furthermore, performance measures in the literature do not surface in the data which raises questions such as to how HU measures student performance. With student related issues in the data, including a relaxed system with unclear boundaries, these shortcomings need addressing. With concerns of students dropping out, systems are relaxed, adding strain on the NEI who, have to find the balance between educating and motivating students whilst executing the desires of the institution.

Little change is mentioned in HU which supports McVeigh's (2002) comments about a lack of significant change in Japanese HE. Institution wide curriculum initiatives were not mentioned but technological advances were. Some negative changes about students were mentioned: the decline in academic ability, and the numbers, and the reduction compulsory

English courses. If change has occurred possibly it has been hard to perceive, which indicates 'consistent and steady management' (Hasegawa, 2010: 15), and would explain the lack in the data. Regardless, the mindset of Japanese work ethic does not appear to exist amongst the NEI showing a lack of acculturation to the host culture. This gap can increase misunderstandings between the NEI and the host culture, and could cause friction amongst the NEI as the literature indicates (see Appendix 1.1).

Lack of, or hindrances to, change do not negate a lack of foresight, but hindrances could have heightened the university's lack of response to the decline in student numbers. It is hard to change things in the university (Glen and Marty), but striking the balance between 'consistent and steady management' (Hasegawa, 2010) and response to external social trends needs to be achieved. This indicates a lack of organisational focus, or direction, and highlights the inability of the current system to adapt and change as McVeigh (2002) stated. With evidence of a top-down structure and the ringi system along with sub-cultures and communication barriers, leadership within the organisation is now discussed.

Leadership

Leadership can bring improvement (Hallinger & Heck, 2011), and while it is said the institute operates by a democratic process, which appears ideal, there are some drawbacks. Ideas that are not accepted by colleagues can be 'quickly eradicated'. This 'democratic' process permits those that don't want change to block it while also creating ways for personal power and concerns to be put before that of the institute, thus preventing positive measures from coming into place. One department cutting compulsory English classes at a time when government measures to internationalise education are already in place

(Yonezawa, 2003) reveals this 'democratic' operating system can hinder positive change. With such processes a lack of unity can clearly reduce effectiveness, as Tierney (1988) warns.

Within the fabric of the institution there is no mention of distributed leadership, or leadership teams (Harris, 2010), functioning, or being encouraged. Nor is there evidence of developing teachers' capacities (Leithwood et al., 2005). Furthermore, systems and processes within which leadership can function to create opportunities to bring knowledge and understanding (Caldwell & Spinks, 1998) are not only lacking, but if put in place could facilitate both school improvement (Hallinger & Heck, 2011) and unity among the NEI. Japanese leadership is voted in every two years, yet there is no evidence of the native tenured English instructors being voted in to lead the NEI.

Some NEI are not sure of what department they belong to, and who the head of department is. Confusion over the tenured staff being able to take authority that was not given to them, and presenting themselves as the boss, coupled with evidence of the tenured staff having authority over which part time instructors should work at HU makes the extent of this authority unclear, causing stress. Claims of power issues which affect trust also need to be resolved. The organisation needs to make clear the leadership roles and authority structure within the institution.

Of the four characteristics of high-performing leadership teams (Bush & Glover, 2012) three are clearly not completely permeating HU. With top-down scenarios, a lack of clear focus, and little coherence and unity being the current situation at HU, there is room for these

elements to be fostered within the leadership of the organisation. Furthermore, leadership can have huge potential to increase change (Thoonen et al., 2012) and bring improvement (Hallinger & Heck, 2011) however from the data, it is evident this can cut both ways. Thus, change in relation to leadership is now examined.

Middlehurst and Elton (1992) indicate that management might be responsible for managing change, and leadership responsible for leading change. While the administration staff, or management of the institution, are praised for being organised and efficient, there is nothing further in the data. What tools the leadership has to lead any change is unclear. The tenured NEI leadership are trying to be proactive but there is doubt whether some of the skills mentioned by Fullan & Scott (2009) and Smith (2008) are present. Regardless, without the infrastructure to support those skills creating a reputation beyond the General English unit (Bryman, 2007) is out of reach. Finally, distributed leadership, and leadership development and improvement, that are mentioned in the literature are not found in the data.

The lack of a clear authority and leadership structures clearly cause confusion within the group of native instructors. The data shows that even some Japanese find it challenging to understand this system. For the native instructors issues arise from this, including a lack of understanding of the leadership structure, accountability, power issues and stress. Embedded in the organisational culture and leadership frameworks lies teamwork, which is discussed next.

Teamwork

Teamwork is another of the key elements to the success of the operator culture (Schein, 2010b) however, evidence of relationship building, which is a fundamental starting point for teamwork (Hackman & Wageman, 2005) and effects performance in multicultural teams (Ang & Van Dyne, 2008), is not found in the data. Likewise, a lack of teamwork between the NEI and Japanese faculty is apparent. Among the NEI there is conflict between some of the participants enjoying freedom and autonomy, and those seeking to work as part of a team. These conflicting perspectives cause a dichotomy. Furthermore, resistance (Kotter, 2012) to, plus some unaddressed apprehension towards, teamwork amongst the NEI, exists due to a number of reasons which include: painful past experiences, a lack of understanding how powerful and motivating it is (Morrison, 1998), and also how the teams are put together (Austin & Baldwin, 1991). The elements for effective teamwork (Ulloa & Adams, 2004) are not present in the data, and added to this is evidence of staff turnover which hinders teamwork (Playford et al., 2000). Furthermore, for some NEI there is opportunity to meet with colleagues only once a year. Currently the data shows that instructors are asked to work together, but then left to define their own boundaries, causing concern. Teamwork having to go at the pace of the weakest member also causes concern, which can hinder teamwork (Atwal & Caldwell, 2006). Furthermore, cautions from Austin & Baldwin (1991) about power emerge, which will ultimately threaten teamwork, plus the data shows pressure has been used to establish teamwork which has produced long-term negative results.

Ways for collaborative planning need to be made for organisational health and effectiveness (Hargreaves, 1992). There is a desire for, but absence of, a physical location to foster collaboration amongst the NEI, and with the Japanese instructors, which results in feelings

of isolation. This lack of facilities illustrates a failure to foster environments conducive to teamwork and collaboration. The rift between the Japanese teachers and the native instructors indicates further hindrances to relationship building. As Japanese put relationship before task (Smith, 1992) this rift accentuates the existence of sub-cultures and the lack of systems to support relationship building. Another possible hindrance to the Japanese and NEI forming closer relationships could be the lack of unity amongst the NEI, but it is possible that this situation is only an indication of a culture that pervades the university with a lack of interdepartmental coordination and communication. The degree to which one part of the institute is fragmented emerges in the data, but with the factors discussed under organisational culture, it is very possible the entire institution suffers from fragmentation. To verify this theory, further investigation is needed.

Further to straightforward teamwork is the fact that the participants are from four different nations. This adds complexity as there are issues concerning MCTs (multi-cultural teams) of which two are pertinent to this study. First, having a common goal (Shokef & Erez, 2008) is a marker of MCTs. While the NEI are all employed to teach English in one institution, beyond this there appears to be no other common goal. Second, cultural islands need to work at getting along better (Schein, 2010a). From the data the annual meeting contributes towards this. However, interpersonal relations have been affected by a lack of communication, unity and leadership issues, as well as issues in the organisational culture discussed above.

The data reveals a number of issues hindering teamwork including concerns within the group, and a lack of tools and systems to support it in the organisational culture. Added to

this, two elements for MCTs are also lacking which suggests the participants need to actively work at furthering relations with each other in the group, as well as needing clear defined goals with measurable outcomes. However, further to the obstacles that are apparent in the data, mentioned above, hindrances caused by cultural differences are now discussed.

Cultural Influences

It was beyond the scope of this investigation to collect data concerning the perspectives of the Japanese instructors, and thus the data from the NEI gives a limited perspective. However, from the data there is a divide between the Japanese and native instructors which creates a number of hurdles. The data indicates the NEI desire a deeper relationship with their Japanese colleagues but it has not been achieved. Only one participant showed appreciation for the way Japanese conduct business. Rumours may have added to a lack of motivation to build relationships between the NEI and the Japanese instructors and visa versa. However, the lack of interaction may be due to complacency, or apathy (Kotter, 2012), or a lack of perceived opportunity, a lack of understanding of the organisational culture or the Japanese culture, or, as stated above, the lack of systems or strong sub-cultures, or a combination of any of these.

While Japanese corporations may not suffer from 'negative ethical implications' (Taka & Foglia, 1994: 135) like their US counterparts, when a Japanese organisation employs a group of westerners, there are ramifications to be considered. Ambiguity over the roles and authority of the tenured staff have emerged in this study. An accountability system for all instructors within the university, across each department is wanting. Consequently, feelings

of distrust, isolation and vulnerability, which are barriers to building collaboration (Chua et al., 2012), exist amongst the group of NEI, which have taken 'years to build'. The path to having values exhibited by high performing schools (Harris, 2010) looks steep.

Having examined the factors enabling and constraining institutional improvement amongst the NEI at HU a number of critical issues have surfaced. The organisational goals are unclear, there is a lack of unity across departments, leading to frustrations and frictions. Accountability structures (Keen, 2003) and faculty collaboration (Rosenholtz, 1989) are wanting and there appears to be no accountability between faculties. Furthermore, faculties appear to be working oblivious to the institution, and other faculties, which indicates an absence of Smith's (2008) six tenets of change for leadership. The communication barriers are producing far reaching effects. The institution does not have a coordinated curriculum with clear goals, which leadership can nurture and oversee, plus there is an anarchic system that is dictated to by a black book, confirming rituals over relationships through which change is being hindered. The result is discord amongst the NEI.

Conclusions

Suspensions of a lack of complete job satisfaction were aroused by the early retirement of a long-standing professor, which coupled with discord amongst a group of western English instructors working together in one university, prompted an initial enquiry into factors effecting motivation amongst the group of native English instructors (NEI). However, as the initial investigation progressed questions arose and the need for further analysis of the data became apparent, which led to this investigation. Through this investigation the initial suspicions were not only confirmed but a number of areas of concern were exposed.

The complexity and context of the investigation was well suited to a case study approach which opened the way for qualitative data to be collected. Qualitative data from fourteen instructors who voluntarily agreed to participate in the investigation was collected through private semi-structured interviews that used a six point tool (Appendix 3). This opened the way for 'rich and relevant data' (Ribbins, 2007: 207) to be collected. The data collection was relatively easy. Participants were obliging, but as with the teaching profession, the participants were busy which required flexibility. However, interviews are complex. With handling perceptions of a situation, the potential for discrepancies to arise is high. Therefore, the reliability of the data has to be evaluated, which calls for triangulation which was achieved through data source triangulation (Chow, 2008). Interviews were the only method of data collection which limits the data to 'claims about what people say' (ibid.), not what they do.

'Rich, thick description' (Creswell, 2012: 252) from the participants demonstrated a degree of trust, but also indicated a lack of having had their concerns heard. The dilemma of an inexperienced researcher handling such quantities of sensitive data threatened the research. It took months to process the data, exposing the underlying issues which are presented. With the aim of this investigation to suggest ways forward in the current situation, the issue of giving precise and detailed exposure to issues, that could cause further impediment to improvement, if once again exposed, was carefully considered. With sensitive data and, adhering to ethical procedures, arduous measures were taken to protect anonymity which then threatened to cloud a clear and illuminative picture. In order to preserve the wholeness of the data, details of posts participants had in the institution was informative, however, a complete description could compromise participant protection.

For a novice researcher the findings were not predicable. The rich descriptions are like symptoms of a disease, they only reveal the effects of underlying issues, and not the cause. The causes had to be carefully picked out, which required an appreciation of the *mélange* of cultures and organizational culture within which this investigation lies. Great care was taken, as researcher, to be as invisible as possible and portray the feelings the participants expressed, untainted. Furthermore, interpretive validity and member checking were used. However, the researchers' 'lens' can never be eliminated (Maxwell, 2012: 124). Trustworthiness of the data was also threatened by fact of being a researcher amongst colleagues. Inevitably, relationships with participants were of various depth, and an effort to keep neutrality in the interview process was sometimes challenging.

As solo researcher, all the data was handled, transcribed by one person before being respondent validated. The Miles & Huberman framework (Punch, 2009) was used for coding and categorising the data. Themes were taken from the literature review, the interviews were printed out and the summarizing, coding and memo taking of data was done by hand. Data display was varied, peeling back the layers, honing down patterns and themes to reveal and generate theories that were tested and confirmed 'with a formalized body of knowledge' (ibid.: 346) resulting in the interpretation and explanation of the investigation.

Whilst this study may also be of possible interest to others in similar situations its aim is not for transferability where laws and theories can be established. Nevertheless, those in situations similar to this context may find the results interesting.

This investigation does not take into account the opinions of the Japanese instructors and as such renders this paper with a narrow perspective. Further research into the organisation as a whole, including the executive culture and engineering culture (Schein, 2010b), would provide a fuller and more coherent picture. This would entail examining communication, teamwork and trust within and between each culture.

There are findings and recommendations arising from this research for the institution and the NEI, with overlapping issues. First are the findings and recommendations for the institution, followed by those for the NEI.

Across the entire institution more cohesion and coordination is needed. The pitfalls of an overly democratic organizational culture become exposed and an overall lack of clear goals,

roles and functions have created voids in which disgruntlement has settled. With clear inter- and intra-departmental communication pathways established, fortified and woven into the culture of the institution, information exchange can be increased and isolation decreased. 'Consistent and steady management' (Hasegawa, 2010: 15) has created an imbalance hindering the ability to respond to external and internal needs. A critical view of foresight is desperately needed. As current social trends are affecting the educational sector nationally, HU is being hit hard due to a lack of response which could have been avoided. The organizational culture of the institution needs to be adjusted to provide more fluid means for change. There is a serious threat if this not attained. Currently pockets of committees within the layers of decision-making authorities are a part of an archaic system that is not only hard to decipher, but also hinders change. While HU is considered democratic and open, this has backfired in an atmosphere where trust is lacking and people are inwardly focused. It is time for a re-examination and for changes to be made.

Furthermore, the lack of fundamental building blocks on which to build collaboration and group work impacts the institution and sub-cultures, which results in a lack of trust, confidence, core values (Harris, 2010), two-way communication, a focus on standards, and internal coherence and unity (Bush & Glover, 2012). It is critical for measures to be taken to ensure transparent parameters for healthy teamwork to flourish in.

By understanding the facilitators and hindrances that exist in the organizational culture of the institution, and through a deeper understanding of the culture, the NEI can improve their current situation. Clear, transparent, two-way communication pathways within the group of NEI need to be established in which information can be exchanged (Bush & Glover, 2012).

This will help create an atmosphere of trust. A guidance for new instructors is necessary (see Appendix 4). Negotiations through discussion, and establishing clear decision making processes, will help reduce resistance within the group (Schein, 2010b). Within the group establishing monitoring systems, as well as trust and confidence, may enhance student outcomes (Harris, 2010). Clear goal setting (Playford et al., 2000) and increased relations within the teams (Ulloa & Adams, 2004) will help reduce hindrances to teamwork. Furthermore, understanding the potential impact of teams (Kotter, 2012) is pivotal. Finally, clear hiring and dismissal practices will improve relations and teamwork.

Suggestions for further research are two-fold. In keeping with the focus of this paper on one institution, the first would be to investigate the perceptions of Japanese colleagues within the same institution drawing from different departments so as to broaden the sources of data and to gain an overall picture of the operator culture (Schein, 2010b) of the institution. The second would be to execute an investigation into the engineering and executive cultures of the institution, thus giving an overall coherent picture of the institution from which alignment of the cultures can be examined (ibid.), and overall institutional improvements suggested.

This investigation has found there are a number of factors among the NEI that are perceived to be facilitating and hindering institutional improvement. With the impact of these factors having been unearthed through the literature, suggestions for smoother working within the institution have been made. The guidance for new instructors (Appendix 6) has been proposed and agreed upon, and it is hoped the recommendations for the group of NEI will be considered, discussed and implemented as the new academic year approaches.

References

- Amey, M.J. (2006) Leadership in Higher Education, Change. In *The Magazine of Higher Learning*, Vol.38, No.6, pp.55-58.
- Ang, S., & Van Dyne, L. (eds.) (2008) *Handbook of Cultural Intelligence: Theory, Measurement, and Applications*. New York:ME Sharpe.
- Appelbaum, S. H., Shapiro, B., & Elbaz, D. (1998) The Management of Multicultural Group Conflict. In *Team Performance Management*, Vol.4, No.5, pp.211-234.
- Atwal, A., & Caldwell, K. (2006) Nurses' Perceptions of Multidisciplinary Teamwork in Acute Health-Care. In *International Journal of Nursing Practice*, Vol.12, No.6, pp.359-365.
- Austin, A. E., & Baldwin, R. G. (1991) Faculty Collaboration: Enhancing the Quality of Scholarship and Teaching. In *ASHE-ERIC Higher Education Report No. 7*. Washington D.C.:ERIC. <http://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED346805.pdf> (17/01/15).
- Baez, B. (2002) Confidentiality in Qualitative Research: Reflection on Secret, Power and Agency. In Briggs, A.R.J., & Coleman, M. (eds.) *Research Methods in Educational Leadership and Management*. London:Sage Publications, p.118.
- Barker, B. (2005) *Transforming Schools: Illusion or Reality?* UK:Trentham Books.
- Barker, B. (2006) The Leadership Paradox: Can School Leaders Transform Student Outcomes? In *School Effectiveness and School Improvement*, Vol.18, No.1, pp.21-43.
- Basit, T.N. (2010) *Conducting Research in Educational Contexts*. London:Continuum.
- Bassey, M. (1999) *Case Study Research in Educational Settings*. Buckingham. UK:McGraw-Hill International.
- Bassey, M. (2007) Case Studies. In Briggs, A.R.J., & Coleman, M. (eds.) *Research Methods in Educational Leadership and Management*. London:Sage Publications, pp.142-155.

Begley, P. T., & Johansson, O. (eds.) (2003) *The Ethical Dimensions of School Leadership*. The Netherlands:Kluwer Academic Publishers.

Bell, J. (2007) The Trouble with Questionnaires. In Briggs, A.R.J., & Coleman, M. (eds.) *Research Methods in Educational Leadership and Management*. London:Sage Publications, pp.224-236.

Bennett, N., Crawford, M., & Riches, C. (eds.) (1992) *Managing Change in Education: Individual and Organizational Perspectives*. London:SAGE.

Bertagni, L. R. (2010) *Glocal Working. Living and Working Across the World with Cultural Intelligence*. Italy:FrancoAngeli.

Black, J. S., Morrison, A. J., & Gregersen, H. B. (1999) *Global Explorers: The Next Generation of Leaders*. Routledge:New York.

Briggs, A.R.J., & Coleman, M. (eds.) (2007) *Research Methods in Educational Leadership and Management*. London:Sage Publications.

Briggs, A.R.J., Coleman, M., & Morrison, M. (eds.) (2012) *Research Methods in Educational Leadership and Management*. London:Sage Publications.

Bryman, A. (2007) Effective Leadership in Higher Education: a Literature Review. In *Studies in Higher Education*, Vol.32, No.6, pp.693-710.

Buchanan, D., & Bryman, A. (eds.) (2009) *The Sage Handbook of Organizational Research Methods*. London:Sage Publications Ltd.

Burgess, R. G. (2002) *In the Field: An Introduction to Field Research*. New York: Routledge.

Burgess, R. G. (ed.) (2005) *The Ethics of Educational Research*. East Sussex:Routledge.

Bush, T. (2012) Authenticity in Research: Reliability, Validity and Triangulation. In Briggs, A.R.J., Coleman, M., & Morrison, M. (eds.) *Research Methods in Educational Leadership and Management*. London:Sage Publications, pp.75-89.

Bush, T. & Glover, D. (2012) Distributed Leadership in Action: Leading High Performing Leadership Teams in English Schools. In *School Leadership & Management: Formerly School Organisation*, Vol.32, No.1, pp.21-36.

Bush, T., & Middlewood, D. (2013) *Leading and Managing People in Education*. London:Sage.

Busher, H., & James, N. (2007) Ethics of Research in Education: An Agenda for Discussion. In Briggs, A.R.J., & Coleman, M. (eds.) *Research Methods in Educational Leadership and Management*. London:Sage Publications, pp.106-122.

Caldwell, B., & Spinks, J. (1998) *Beyond the Self-Managing School*. London:Falmer Press.

Cassell, C. (2009) Interviews in Organizational Research. In Buchanan, D., & Bryman, A. (eds.) *The Sage Handbook of Organizational Research Methods*. London:Sage Publications Ltd, pp.500-515.

Chapman, C., & Harris, A. (2004) Improving Schools in Difficult and Challenging Contexts: Strategies for Improvement. In *Educational Research*, Vol.46, No.3, pp.219-228.

Cheng, C. Y., Sanchez-Burks, J., & Lee, F. (2008) Connecting the Dots Within Creative Performance and Identity Integration. In *Psychological Science*, Vol.19, No.11, pp. 1178-1184.

Chow, A. S. Y. (2008) *The Role of Systems Design and Educational Informatics in Educational Reform: The Story of the Central Educational Center*. MI:ProQuest.

Chua, R. Y., & Morris, M. W. (2009) *Innovation Communication in Multicultural Networks: Deficits in Inter-cultural Capability and Affect-based Trust as Barriers to New Idea Sharing*

in *Inter-Cultural Relationships*. HBS. MA:Unpublished. http://www.hbs.edu/faculty/Publication%20Files/09-130_025221b6-e35a-49d0-affb-6466a4a008ac.pdf (18/01/15).

Chua, R. Y., Morris, M. W., & Mor, S. (2012) Collaborating Across Cultures: Cultural Metacognition and Affect-based Trust in Creative Collaboration. In *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, Vol.118, No.2, pp.116-131.

Cohen, L., Manion, L., & Morrison, K. (2007) *Research Methods in Education 6th Edition*. London:Routledge.

Coleman, M. (2012) Interviews. In Briggs, A.R.J., Coleman, M., & Morrison, M. (eds.) *Research Methods in Educational Leadership and Management*. London:Sage Publications, pp.250-265.

Cooper, M., Burman, E., Ling, L., Razdevsek-Pucko, C., & Stephenson, J. (1998) Practical Strategies in Values Education. *Values in Education*. London:Routledge.

Covey, S.R. (1999) Foreword. In Black, J. S., Morrison, A. J., & Gregersen, H. B. *Global Explorers: The Next Generation of Leaders*. Routledge:New York, pp. v-viii.

Creese, A. (2005) *Teacher Collaboration and Talk in Multilingual Classrooms*. Clevedon, UK:Multilingual Matters.

Creswell, J.W. (2012) *Qualitative Inquiry and Research Design Choosing Among Five Traditions*. Thousand Oaks, CA:Sage.

Creswell, J.W. (2013) *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches*. California:Sage.

Deakin, H., & Wakefield, K. (2014) Skype Interviewing: Reflections of Two PhD

Researchers. In *Qualitative Research*, Vol.14, No.5, pp. 603–616. <http://qrj.sagepub.com/content/early/2013/05/24/1468794113488126.full.pdf+html> (24/01/15).

- Deem, R. (1998) 'New Managerialism' and Higher Education: the Management of Performances and Cultures in Universities in the United Kingdom. In *International Studies in Sociology of Education*, Vol.8, No.1, pp.47-70.
- Denison, E.F., & Chung, W.K. (1976) *How Japan's Economy Grew So Fast*. Brookings:Washington D.C.
- Denscombe, M. (2010) *The Good Research Guide: for Small-Scale Social Research Projects*. Berkshire:Open University Press.
- Denzin, N.K. (2009) The Elephant in the Living Room: or Extending the Conversation about the Politics of Evidence. In *Qualitative Research*, Vol.9, No.2, pp.139-160.
- Denzin, N.K., & Ryan, K.E. (2007) Qualitative Methodology (Including Focus Groups). In Outhwaite, W., & Turner, S. (eds.) *The SAGE Handbook of Social Science Methodology*. London:Sage, pp.578-594.
- Dimmock, C. (2005) *Designing the Learning-Centred School: A Cross-Cultural Perspective*. London:Falmer Press.
- Dorfman, P.W. & House, R.J. (2004) Cultural Influences on Organizational Leadership. In House, R.J., Hanges, P.J., Javidan, M., Dorfman, P.W., & Gupta, V. (eds.) *Culture, Leadership, and Organizations: The GLOBE Study of 62 Societies*. Thousand Oaks, CA:Sage, pp.51-73.
- Earley, P. C., & Ang, S. A. (2003) *Cultural Intelligence: Individual Interactions Across Cultures*. California:Stanford University Press.
- Earley, P. C., & Mosakowski, E. (2004) Cultural Intelligence. In *Harvard Business Review*, Vol.82, No.10, pp.139-146.
- Fey, C. F., & Denison, D. R. (2003) Organizational Culture and Effectiveness: Can American Theory Be Applied in Russia? In *Organization Science*, Vol.14, No.6, pp.686-706.

- Franklin, M.I. (2012) *Understanding Research: Coping with the Quantitative Qualitative Data Divide*. Oxon:Routledge.
- Fullan, M., & Scott, G. (2009) *Turnaround Leadership for Higher Education*. CA:John Wiley & Sons.
- Goldman, R. (2004) Video Perspectivity Meets Wild and Crazy Teens: A Design Ethnography. In *Cambridge Journal of Education*, Vol.34, No.2, pp.157-178.
- Gorard, S. (2003) *Quantitative Methods in Social Science Research*. Continuum:London.
- Greatbach, D. (2009) Conversation Analysis in Organization Research. In Buchanan, D., & Bryman, A. (eds.) *The Sage Handbook of Organizational Research Methods*. London:Sage Publications Ltd., pp.484-499.
- Guba, E. & Lincoln, Y. (1981) Effective Evaluation. In Briggs, A.R.J., & Coleman, M. (eds.) *Research Methods in Educational Leadership and Management*. London:Sage Publications, p.209.
- Guba, E. G. (ed.) (1990) *The Paradigm Dialog*. California:Sage Publications.
- Hackman, J. R., & Wageman, R. (2005) A Theory of Team Coaching. In *Academy of Management Review*, Vol.30, No.2, pp.269-287.
- Haghirian, P. (2010) *Understanding Japanese Management Practices*. New York:Business Expert Press.
- Hallinger, P. and Heck, R. (2011) Exploring the Journey of School Improvement: Classifying and Analysing Patterns of Change in School Improvement Processes and Learning Outcomes. In *School Effectiveness and School Improvement*, Vol.22, No.1, pp. 1-27.
- Hanna, P. (2012) Using Internet Technologies (such as Skype) as a Research Medium: a Research Note. In *Qualitative Research*, Vol.12, No.2, pp.239-242.

- Hargreaves, A. (1992) *Contrived Collegiality: The Micropolitics of Teacher Collaboration*. In Bennett, N., Crawford, M., & Riches, C. (eds.) *Managing Change in Education: Individual and Organizational Perspectives*. London:SAGE, pp.80-94.
- Harris, A. (2010) *Distributed Leadership*. In Bush, T., Bell, L., and Middlewood, D. (eds.) *The Principles of Educational Leadership and Management*. London: Sage, pp.55-69.
- Harris, A., & Muijs, D. (2004) *Improving Schools Through Teacher Leadership*. USA: McGraw-Hill International.
- Harris, M.M., & Lievens, F. (2005) *Selecting Employees for Global Assignments: Can Assessment Centers Measure Cultural Intelligence?* In Rahim, M. A., Golembiewski, R. T., & Mackenzie, K. D. (eds.) *Current Topics in Management*, Vol.8. New Brunswick, N.J.: Transaction Publishers, pp.221-420.
- Hasegawa, Y. (2010) *Rediscovering Japanese Business Leadership: 15 Japanese Managers and the Companies They're Leading to New Growth*. Wiley:Singapore.
- Hashimoto, K. (2009) *Cultivating Japanese Who can use English: Problems and Contradictions in Government Policy*. In *Asian Studies Review*, Vol.33, No.1, pp.21–42.
- Hatch, J. A. (2002) *Doing Qualitative Research in Education Settings*. NY:SUNY Press.
- Hemphill, J. K., & Coons, A. E. (1957) *Development of the Leader Behaviour Description Questionnaire*. In Stogdill, R. M., & Coons, A. E. (eds.) *Leader Behaviour: Its Description and Measurement*. Columbus, OH:Ohio State University Press, pp.6-38.
- Hofstede, G. (1993) *Cultural Constraints in Management Theories*. In *The Academy of Management Executive*, Vol.7, No.1, pp.81-94.
- Hofstede, G., & Bond, M. H. (1984) *Hofstede's Culture Dimensions An Independent Validation Using Rokeach's Value Survey*. In *Journal of Cross-Cultural Psychology*, Vol.15, No.4, pp.417-433.

- Itoh, A. (2002) Higher Education Reform in Perspective: The Japanese Experience. In *Higher Education*, Vol.43, No.1, pp.7–25.
- Janghorban, R., Roudsari, R. L., & Taghipour, A. (2014) Skype interviewing: The New Generation of Online Synchronous Interview in Qualitative Research. In *International Journal of Qualitative Studies on Health and Well-being*, 9. <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3991833/> (24/01/15).
- James, N., & Busher, H. (2009) *Online Interviewing*. London:Sage.
- Johnson, R. R. B., & Christensen, L. B. (2010) *Educational Research: Quantitative, Qualitative, and Mixed Approaches*. California:Sage Publications.
- Kariya, T. (2012) *Higher Education and the Japanese Disease*. <http://www.nippon.com/en/in-depth/a00602/> (09/05/13).
- Keen, T. R. (2003) *Creating Effective & Successful Teams*. USA:Purdue University Press.
- Kezar, A., & Eckel, P.D. (2002) The Effect of Institutional Culture on Change Strategies in Higher Education: Universal Principles or Culturally Responsive Concepts? In *The Journal of Higher Education*, Vol.73, No.4, pp.435-460.
- Knight, P.T., & Trowler. P. R. (2000) Department-level Cultures and the Improvement of Learning and Teaching. In *Studies in Higher Education*, Vol.25, No,1, pp.69-83.
- Knight, W. H., & Holen, M. C. (1985) Leadership and the Perceived Effectiveness of Department Chairpersons. In Bryman, A. Effective Leadership in Higher Education: a Literature Review. In *Studies in Higher Education*, Vol.32, No.6, pp.693-710.
- Kotter, J.P. (1996) *Leading Change*. Boston:Harvard Business Press.
- Kotter, J.P. (2012) *Leading Change*. Boston:Harvard Business Press.
- Kvale, S. (2007) Doing Interviews. In Briggs, A.R.J., Coleman, M., & Morrison, M. *Research Methods in Educational Leadership & Management*. London:Sage, p.260.

- Lee, C.H., & Templer, K.J. (2003) Cultural Intelligence Assessment and Measurement. In Earley, P. C., & Ang, S. A. *Cultural Intelligence: Individual Interactions Across Cultures*. California:Stanford University Press, pp.185-208.
- Leithwood, K., Harris, A., & Hopkins, D. (2008) Seven Strong Claims About Successful School Leadership. In *School Leadership & Management: Formerly School Organisation*, Vol.28, No.1, pp.27-42.
- Lincoln, J. R., & Kalleberg, A. L. (1990) *Culture, Control and Commitment: A Study of Work Organization and Work Orientations in the United States and Japan*. Cambridge: CUP.
- Lincoln, Y. S., & Guba, E. G. (1985) Naturalist Inquiry. In Bassey, M. *Case Study Research in Educational Settings*. Buckingham. UK: McGraw-Hill International, p.75.
- Livermore, D. (2009) *Leading with Cultural Intelligence: The New Secret to Success*. New York:AMACOM.
- Livermore, D. (2011) The Cultural Intelligence Difference Special Ebook Edition: *Master the One Skill You Can't Do Without in Today's Global Economy*. New York:AMACOM.
- Lussier, R. N., & Achua, C. F. (2009) *Leadership: Theory, Application, & Skill Development*. Mason, OH:Cengage Learning.
- Machado, C., & Melo, P. (eds.) (2014) *Effective Human Resources Management in Small and Medium Enterprises: Global Perspectives*. USA:IGI Global.
- Malcolm, J. (2011) *The Journalist and the Murderer*. London:Granta Books.
- Maxwell, J. A. (2012) *Qualitative Research Design: An Interactive Approach*. California: Sage.
- McVeigh, B. J. (2002) *Japanese Higher Education as Myth*. New York:Sharpe.
- Mercer, J., Barker, B., & Bird, R. (2010) *Human Resource Management in Education: Context, Themes and Impact*. Oxon:Routledge.

- Middlehurst, R., & Elton, L. (1992) Leadership and Management in Higher Education. In *Studies in Higher Education*, Vol.17, No.3, pp.251-264.
- Miles, M. B., & Huberman, A. M. (1994) *Qualitative Data Analysis: An Expanded Sourcebook*. California:Sage.
- Miles, M. B., & Huberman, A. M. (1994) Qualitative Data Analysis: An Expanded Sourcebook. In Punch, K. F. *Introduction to Research Methods in Education*. London:Sage, pp. 173-180.
- Miles, M. B., Huberman, A. M., & Saldaña, J. (2013) *Qualitative Data Analysis: A Methods Sourcebook*. California:Sage Publications.
- Mills, A. J., Durepos, G., & Wiebe, E. (eds.) (2009) *Encyclopedia of Case Study Research* (Vol.2). California:Sage Publications.
- Mischel, W. (2004) Toward an Integrative Science of the Person. In *Annual Review of Psychology*, Vol.55, pp.1-22.
- Morrison, K. (1998) *Management Theories for Educational Change*. London:Paul Chapman.
- Morrison, M. (2012) Understanding Methodology. In Briggs, A.R.J., Coleman, M., & Morrison, M. (eds.) *Research Methods in Educational Leadership and Management*. London:Sage Publications, pp.14-36.
- Moua, M. (2011) *Culturally Intelligent Leadership: Leading Through Intercultural Interactions*. New York:Business Expert Press.
- Nagatomo, D. (2012) *Exploring Japanese University English Teachers' Professional Identity*, Vol.23. Bristol:Multilingual Matters.
- Nakano, C. (1997) A Survey Study of Japanese Managers' Views of Business Ethics. In *Journal of Business Ethics*, Vol.16, No.16, pp.1737-1751.

- Ng, K. Y., Van Dyne, L., Ang, S., & Ryan, A. M. (2012) Cultural Intelligence: A Review, Reflections, and Recommendations for Future Research. *Conducting Multinational Research Projects in Organizational Psychology*, Washington, DC:American Psychological Association.
- Ogawa, R. & Bossert, S. (1995) Leadership as an Organizational Quality. In *Educational Administration Quarterly*, Vol.31, No.2, pp.224–243.
- Ogawa, Y. (2002) Challenging the Traditional Organization of Japanese Universities. In *Higher Education*, Vol.43, No.1, pp.85-108.
- Ouchi, W. (1981) Theory Z: How American Business Can Meet the Japanese Challenge. In Lussier, R. N., & Achua, C. F. *Leadership: Theory, Application, & Skill Development*. Mason, OH:Cengage Learning, pp.153-154.
- Outhwaite, W., & Turner, S. (eds.) (2007) *The SAGE Handbook of Social Science Methodology*. London:Sage.
- Playford, E. D., Dawson, L., Limbert, V., Smith, M., Ward, C. D., & Wells, R. (2000) Goal-Setting in Rehabilitation: Report of a Workshop to Explore Professionals' Perceptions of Goal-Setting. In *Clinical Rehabilitation*, Vol.14, No.5, pp.491-496.
- Peterson, R.A. (2005) In Search of Authenticity. In *Journal of Management Studies*, Vol.45, No.5, pp.1083-1098.
- Punch, K. F. (2009) *Introduction to Research Methods in Education*. London:Sage.
- Rahim, M. A., Golembiewski, R. T., & Mackenzie, K. D. (eds.) (2005) *Current Topics in Management*, Vol.8. New Brunswick, N.J.:Transaction Publishers.
- Ribbins, P. (2007) Interviews in Education: Conversations with a Purpose. In Briggs, A.R.J., & Coleman, M. (eds.) *Research Methods in Educational Leadership and Management*. London:Sage Publications, pp.207 - 223.

- Riddell, S. (1989) Exploiting the Exploited? The Ethics of Feminist Educational Research. In Burgess, R. G. (ed.) *The Ethics of Educational Research*. East Sussex:Routledge, pp. 77-99.
- Rosenholtz, S. (1989) Teachers' Workplace: The Social Organization of Schools. In Creese, A. *Teacher Collaboration and Talk in Multilingual Classrooms*. Clevedon, UK:Multilingual Matters, p.107.
- Rubio-Andrés, Gutiérrez-Broncano & Varona-Castillo (2014) Self-Managing Teams in Small and Medium Enterprises. In Machado, C., & Melo, P. (eds.) *Effective Human Resources Management in Small and Medium Enterprises: Global Perspectives*. USA:IGI Global, pp.280-300.
- Rumsey, M. G. (ed.) (2012) *The Oxford Handbook of Leadership*. Oxford:Oxford University Press.
- Sammons, P., Hillman, J., & Mortimore, P. (1995) *Key Characteristics of Effective Schools: a Review of School Effectiveness Research*. London:OFSTED.
- Schein, E. H. (2010a) *Organizational Culture and Leadership* (Vol.2). San Francisco:Jossey-Bass.
- Schein, E. H. (2010b) Three Cultures of Management: the Key to Organizational Learning. In Bertagni, L. R. *Glocal Working. Living and Working Across the World with Cultural Intelligence*. Italy:FrancoAngeli, pp.37-58.
- Scott, D., & Morrison, M. (2006) *Key Ideas in Educational Research*. In Briggs, A.R.J., Coleman, M., & Morrison, M. (eds.) *Research Methods in Educational Leadership and Management*. London:Sage Publications, p.83.
- Seidman, I. (2012) *Interviewing as Qualitative Research: A Guide for Researchers in Education and the Social Sciences*. NY:Teachers College Press.

Sergiovanni, T. J., & Moore, J. H. (eds.) (1989) *Schooling for Tomorrow: Directing Reforms to Issues that Count*. MA:Allyn and Bacon.

Shokef, E. & Erez, M. (2008) Cultural Intelligence and Global Identity in Multicultural Teams. In Ang, S., & Van Dyne, L. (eds.) *Handbook of Cultural Intelligence: Theory, Measurement, and Applications*. New York:ME Sharpe, pp.177-191.

Shulman, L. S. (1989) Teaching Alone, Learning Together: Needed Agendas for the New Reforms. In Sergiovanni, T. J., & Moore, J. H. (eds.) *Schooling for Tomorrow: Directing Reforms to Issues that Count*. MA:Allyn and Bacon, pp.166-187.

Smith, L. (ed.) (2008) *Schools that Change: Evidence-Based Improvement and Effective Change Leadership*. Thousand Oaks, CA:Corwin Press.

Smith, P. B. (1992) Organizational Behaviour and National Cultures. In *British Journal of Management*, Vol.3, No.1, pp.39-51.

Speck, M. (2002) Balanced and Year-Round Professional Development: Time and Learning. In *Catalyst for Change*, Vol.32, No.1, pp.17-19.

Stogdill, R. M., & Coons, A. E. (eds.) (1957) *Leader Behaviour: Its Description and Measurement*. Columbus:Ohio State University Press.

Sullivan, J. R. (2012) Skype: An Appropriate Method of Data Collection for Qualitative Interviews? In *The Hilltop Review*, Vol.6, Iss.1, Article 10, pp.54-60. <http://scholarworks.wmich.edu/hilltopreview/vol6/iss1/10/> (24/01/15).

Taka, I., & Foglia, W. D. (1994) Ethical Aspects of "Japanese Leadership Style". In *Journal of Business Ethics*, Vol.13, No.2, pp.135-148.

Thoonen, E. E., Slegers, P. J., Oort, F. J., & Peetsma, T. T. (2012) Building School-Wide Capacity for Improvement: the Role of Leadership, School Organizational Conditions, and

Teacher Factors. In *School Effectiveness and School Improvement*, Vol.23, No.4, pp. 441-460.

Thorsen, E. (2008) Journalistic objectivity redefined? Wikinews and the Neutral Point of View. In Williams, K. *International Journalism*. London:Sage, p.84.

Tierney, W. G. (1988) Organizational Culture in Higher Education: Defining the Essentials. In *The Journal of Higher Education*, Vol.59, No.1, pp.2-21.

Tsuneyoshi, R. (2001) *Japanese Model of Schooling: Comparisons with the US*. Oxon: Routledge.

Ulloa, B. C. R., & Adams, S. G. (2004) Attitude Toward Teamwork and Effective Teaming. In *Team Performance Management*, Vol.10, No.7/8, pp.145-151.

Walker, A. D. (2003) Developing Cross-Cultural Perspectives on Education and Community. In Begley, P. T., & Johansson, O. (eds.) *The Ethical Dimensions of School Leadership*. The Netherlands:Kluwer Academic Publishers, pp.145-160.

Webster, M. Jr., and Sell, J. (2007) Theory and Experimentation in the Social Sciences. In Outhwaite, W., & Turner, S. (eds.) *The SAGE Handbook of Social Science Methodology*. London:Sage, pp.190-207.

Woodside, A. G. (2010) *Case Study Research: Theory, Methods and Practice: Theory, Methods, Practice*. UK:Emerald Group Publishing.

Yin, R. K. (2013) *Case Study Research: Design and Methods* (5th ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA:Sage Publications.

Yonezawa, A. (2003) The Impact of Globalisation on Higher Education Governance in Japan. In *Higher Education Research & Development*, Vol.22, No.2, pp.145-154.

Yonezawa, A. (2007) Japanese Flagship Universities at a Crossroads. In *Higher Education*, Vol.54, No.4, pp.483-499.

Appendix 1:

Possible Implications of Hofstede's Cultural Dimensions with the NEI Working in HU

1. Power Distance (PD)

This category, over all the other categories, has the highest difference in points within the native cultures of the NEI. Also this category has the least difference to the host culture. This is probably the main area of least conflict. The host culture will have a stronger perception of the existing hierarchy within the institution, but the culture within the NEI can be expected to understand this concept, they may not be as sensitive to the differences in hierarchy and this might lead to misunderstandings when they are evidenced.

2. Individualism vs Collectivism (ID)

The NEI, if they are still attached to their culture of upbringing will value their family over their work relations. The host culture will value work relations over family and expect an uncompromising loyalty to the institution over all other relationships. NEI, in viewing family as more important than work relations, may struggle if the host culture oversteps time and commitment boundaries that may be unspoken, but existent, in the institution.

3. Masculinity vs Femininity (MA)

With middling scores for the countries of the NEI, within the group there may be only a little variation within the group. However, the host culture has a high MA score, so it could be very easy for the host culture to perceive all the NEI as having the same trait here. Conflict may arise within the group if some NEI have taken on the host culture's point of view while some have retained their original culture.

4. Uncertainty Avoidance (UA)

All of the NEI come from countries that have a low score on UA and rank very closely together with only a difference of four points, whilst the host culture has a very high score. It is probable that the NEI may not be able to determine what is ambiguous to the host culture.

5. Long-Term Orientation (LT)

All of the countries represented in the cultures of the NEI at HU have come from countries with low LT. Japan has a high LT. The implications of this could evidence themselves in ways the NEI create short-term goals to bring improvement. In the host culture however, these actions may not be appreciated as the focus is more long-term. Thus a conflict of orientation may arise as NEI suggest ideas, but they seem to fall on 'deaf ears' as the culture of the institution fails to see how these little measures can result in long-term improvement. This could be a point of friction.

Appendix 2:

Letter of Participation

Dear [name of colleague inserted] ,

I hope you are well.

I know we don't see each other around [name of the university inserted], but I am hoping that you will be willing to participate in some research for my Masters Degree in Educational Leadership.

I am looking into organizational effectiveness (what facilitates it, what hinders it). I am asking all the native instructors at [name of the university inserted], if they would be willing to be interviewed for this research. I anticipate the interview will take between 20-30 mins and I am willing to work around your schedule, and location as needs be; I can also interview via Skype if that is the most convenient for you.

I am hoping to conduct interviews from mid-February to early-April, but would like to finish as early as possible.

I am hoping everyone will be willing to voice their frank opinions so I can get some accurate data. Naturally, this research is for academic purposes only, and as such the results will be available for those that participate if they wish to see them. Also for ethical reasons

names will not only be anonymised, but measures will be taken 'to provide as much anonymity as possible' (Mercer et al., 2010).

If you could quickly let me know whether you are willing to participate, or not, this will let me know you have seen this letter.

From there we can set up the most convenient time, place and method for me to interview you.

Thank you very much,

Yours,

Kate

Mercer, J., Barker, B., & Bird, R. 2010 Human Resource Management in Education: Context, Themes and Impact. Oxon, Routledge.

Appendix 3:

Letter No. 2 to Instructors, with Interview Questions

Dear [colleague's name inserted],

Thank you, once again for your willingness to help out with my Masters degree and the current research. I am researching human resource management in education, and in particular I have decided to focus on organizational effectiveness and staff motivation. Here are the questions, and I look forward to hearing your answers in the very near future.

Yours,

Kate

Interview Questions:

1. Tell me about you and the university: How did you get your job, why have you stayed, what do you like and dislike about working at the university?
2. What changes, for better or for worse, have you seen during your time of employment at the university?
3. What are barriers (or hindrances) and what are enablers (or helpers) to effectiveness have you encountered whilst working at the university?
4. Tell me about the leadership at the university; to what extent does this work for you?
5. Tell me about team work at the university - how does this work for you?
6. In your opinion what needs to change or improve at the university?

Appendix 4:

Bassey's Ethical Guidelines: Four Questions

At the first stage

- 1 Has permission been given to conduct the research in terms of the stage one identification of an issue, problem, or hypothesis, in this particular setting?

At the third stage

- 2 What arrangements have been agreed for transferring the ownership of the record of utterances and actions to the researcher, thus enabling the latter to use these in compiling the case record?

At the sixth stage

- 3 What arrangements have been agreed for either identifying or concealing the contributing individuals and the particular setting of the research in the case report?
- 4 What arrangements have been agreed for giving permission to publish the case report?

(Bassey, 1999: 77)

Appendix 5:

Other Institutional Practices Disclosed by the Participants.

<p>1. <u>A Controlling University</u> The 'office watches over everything and so the head of the English department is always under a watchful eye.' The directors 'control everything, so 'we just teach [the] system.' The result of this is that 'everybody complains but the directors of the school are happy.' (Francis)</p>
<p>2. <u>A Relaxed University</u> The 'English classes have no definition' the instructor doesn't 'even use a text book'. The result is 'the students said this is so fun..the attendance was almost perfect.' (Francis)</p>
<p>3. <u>A Listening Department</u> The tenured staff takes suggestions as to which textbook should be taught, but ultimately the decision lies with the staff. This system would work well at HU. (Glen)</p>
<p>4. <u>Team Run, Collaborative Research Culture</u> Instructors work in teams of 6-8 people. All materials are made in house, and the teams write research papers together. (Jules)</p>
<p>5. <u>A Cutting Edge University</u> A university that meets its intake every year because of the high graduate employment rate. The classes at HU should be 'more cutting edge.' (Kim)</p>
<p>6. <u>Co-ordinated Programme</u> A university where there is 'an overarching programme' and teachers share their 'teaching talents and insights.' It is a system that 'work[s] very well' is 'where everyone is on the same text book and they have a university wide test at the end.' (Lee)</p>
<p>7. <u>Team Teaching Classes</u> A different style of team work is where teachers are 'paired up' and share a class for a semester and 'the credits are divided.' Alternatively having a course with three hours a week is divided between two teachers who teach very different lessons is yet another system. (Nat)</p>
<p>8. <u>Democratic Department</u> The whole department (Japanese and native teachers) meet together and everything is decided by a majority vote. 'It is a positive environment there is a lot of trust. People work together.' Problems are discussed. The teachers at that university teach the same book, but they teach it in the way they want to. (Alex)</p>
<p>9. <u>Various Class-Style University</u> The university aims is to 'find the teachers' strengths' and students 'can choose the style of class they want.' (Brett)</p>

Appendix 6:

Guidance for New Teachers

1. A who is who in the university (To include staff in: The General Education Affairs Office, the English Department, the Systems Information office, and International Relations staff, along with all the other part-time and full-time native instructors with the day and time of their classes for that year on a handout).
2. A guided tour of the campuses with a map to take away.
3. An organizational chart of the university.
4. An overview of the English classes/curricula taught by the native speakers in the university.
5. The reason they have been hired, what is expected of them, and how to fulfil those expectations during the year (including clear goals and pathways).
6. A hands-on training on how to use the equipment in the classrooms, and the log in procedure on the computers.
7. A workshop on the basics of Moodle (including how to find their course, how to use the template, sharing cart, blind documents, upload handouts to their course and take attendance, etc.).
8. Printing and photocopying - procedures and paperwork, and general use of the room and equipment.